

Impact monitoring and evaluation framework for DISTENDER

D10.1: DISTENDER KPIs Technical Framework
WP10, T10.1: Selection of KPIs

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Technical references

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Preface

This report defines a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) framework for the EU Horizon project DISTENDER and outlines the general monitoring approach for the project. The monitoring approach is designed and implemented by Work Package 10 – Project Monitoring.

The purpose of the Work Package is to support the members of the project consortium, consisting mainly of researchers, case study representatives, and external stakeholders from the case studies, in becoming clear about, assessing, and optimizing the long-term impacts of their work.

The impact monitoring is deliberately begun at an early stage of the project. This enables the monitoring team to establish baselines early in the project and follow its progress continuously. The present deliverable D10.1 draws up a framework within which all future WP10 deliverables (D10.2; D10.3; D10.4) are going to measure, assess, quantify, and interpret the progress of DISTENDER. The framework is based on a DISTENDER theory of change and defines both outcomes and impacts for the project.

At this stage, the indicator framework is deliberately kept open to allow for further adjustment during the project duration, should individual indicators turn out to be less suited than others for reliable impact monitoring.

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1 Introduction

DISTENDER aims to develop novel interdisciplinary methodologies for designing effective and easy-to-implement climate change strategies and policies. The central thematic focus of the project is the effective integration of climate adaptation and mitigation measures, two topics which are too often understood and treated as conceptually distinct fields of action. The project's core product will be a Decision Support System (DSS) to assist decisionmakers in five core and six follower case studies in weighing options for climate action, assessing their cost-effectiveness, and designing robust strategies to combat the causes and impacts of climate change.

The DISTENDER project consortium works towards ensuring that mitigation and adaptation actions do not conflict with each other, are legitimised politically, and, wherever possible, positively influence one another. Trade-offs, synergies, and conflicts between the two fields of action are identified, analysed and assessed. For this purpose, DISTENDER boasts a strong co-creation element and engages stakeholders from five European core case studies in participatory formats. This emphasis aligns with other European projects like, for example, the SmartEnCity and LOCOMOTION projects (Grant agreement IDs 691883 and 821105, respectively). The case studies will, on the one hand, provide input in terms of data and expertise, and, on the other hand, test and implement the research outputs.

In the grant agreement to the project, nine core objectives were set for the initial project duration of three and a half years. These objectives are formulated so as to emphasise the innovative and unique contributions of the project to both climate science and climate policy, contributions which go beyond the broader aims of enhancing European societies' resilience to climate change and advancing knowledge about climate change's causes and effects:

Table 1: Short list of DISTENDER objectives

	Title
Objective 1	Stakeholder engagement process & participation using co-creation
Objective 2	Participatory development of localized socio-economic scenarios
Objective 3	Produce localized climate storylines through a downscaling framework
Objective 4	Risk and vulnerability assessment based on a set of bio-physical, social and economic indicators produced by a wide range of multi-scale and cross-sectorial models
Objective 5	Robust adaptation and mitigation actions and policies from a suite of harmonized strategies constructed through participatory methods
Objective 6	Sectoral, integrated and economy-wide economic evaluation of climate strategies
Objective 7	Translate scientific results into policy relevant actions
Objective 8	Testing and replication of the outcomes of the project through case studies
Objective 9	Network to promote and exchange the outputs of the projects with other EU and international initiatives about climate change

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The objectives are explicitly linked to individual work packages of DISTENDER. Nevertheless, the holistic and integrated design of the project enables and requires all of the project's twelve work packages to work in unison to best achieve the general project goals. Such multi- and interdisciplinarity are a defining characteristic of DISTENDER and EU Horizon projects generally. While desirable for achieving adequately wide-ranging and multi-perspectival results to address the cross-cutting challenge of climate change and guarantee a high level of diversity and participation, a high level of interdisciplinarity also requires special measures to ensure that both researchers, stakeholders, and the commissioning agency do not lose track of the bigger picture and are able to steer the project towards achieving maximal impact.

In order to link the highly specialized and technical work done in the context of the individual work packages to the achievement of the overarching project objectives, and to maximize DISTENDER's impact, a dedicated monitoring framework is being put in place from the outset of the project work.

Considering other EU projects carrying out monitoring for climate adaptation and mitigation strategies, such as the still-running project POCITYF (Grant agreement ID 864400), in DISTENDER this monitoring focuses on gauging potential short- and long-term positive and negative impacts of the project activities and outputs. Data is collected and assessed from the start of the project throughout for two main reasons: To *track* the progress of the achievement of DISTENDER's potential impacts, and to *maximize* these impacts. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used to collect data on the project's outcomes. As positive outcomes are the precondition for positive impacts, the KPIs aim to describe the essential preconditions for DISTENDER to achieve optimal impact. The long-term impacts are then calculated on the basis of the measured outcomes.

The KPIs will *describe, quantify, and communicate* DISTENDER's impact pathways from a very early stage of the project work onwards. Addressing impacts at such an early stage makes DISTENDER's monitoring approach innovative. The DISTENDER monitoring takes a *formative* approach (see chapter 1.1): The KPIs and their change in value over time will help the whole project consortium gain a clearer picture of what actions need to be taken, which aspects of the work should be prioritized and focused on, and what should be avoided.

The final indicators for monitoring the impact of DISTENDER are a co-production of WP10 and the other work packages of the project. Conceptually, the impacts and KPIs were developed in accordance with the project objectives along ten key 'dimensions' (see chapter 1.4) to facilitate a cross-sectional approach and anticipate potential impacts beyond the mere execution of the individual tasks as outlined in the project proposal.

Part of the work done in preparation for this report included the scanning of existing indicator frameworks at European and national level. In the definition of outcomes and impacts, several ongoing EU Horizon 2020 projects have been considered, most of them focusing on climate adaptation and mitigation strategies. For this review, the net was cast wide and climate-related research projects were examined according to indicator frameworks used within them to monitor the success of implemented actions.

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The present report is divided into two main parts: The first part (chapter 1) deals with theoretical questions of impact monitoring generally and constructs a theory of change for DISTENDER specifically. The second part substantiates this theory with a system of Key Performance indicators which will be utilized to measure specific outcomes of the project and assess its longer-term impacts.

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2 Theoretical framework

This first chapter provides the theoretical foundation for the DISTENDER approach to monitoring and evaluation. It outlines the focal areas chosen, and the methods to be applied in the monitoring of the project. The present chapter defines key terms, and constructs a general impact pathway and, based on this, a theory of change for the DISTENDER project in particular. The DISTENDER ‘impact dimensions’ are elaborated on and developed into a Key Performance Indicator framework for monitoring the impact of the project.

The theoretical framework development mainly draws on two types of source material: a) relevant *peer-reviewed literature* on the general topics of impact assessment and project evaluation, and on specific topics such as co-creation, science-policy interaction, or uncertainty analysis; and b) results, deliverables, and methods from *previous* and *current research projects* at both national and EU level, many of them participants in the EU funding scheme Horizon 2020. A list with all such projects scanned for this report is provided in Annex I, the individual chapters of the report reference individual projects when they are of direct relevance to the work conducted for DISTENDER. Additionally, the DISTENDER grant agreement was consulted in detail throughout the work on this report and is referenced where relevant.

2.1 DISTENDER approach to monitoring and evaluation

A whole work package of the DISTENDER project is dedicated to the activity of ‘Project Monitoring’. This is unusual and attributes high significance to the constant and continuous reflection on the research activities of the project consortium while they are being undertaken. This extensive reflective activity serves three central purposes: a) Qualified feedback from the multiple target groups and stakeholders of the project is regularly collected and can be considered in the progressing implementation of the project in order to maximize the project’s impact; b) project progress, project results, and project impacts will be made communicable to interested outside observers and will boost the reach of the project beyond its immediate target groups; and c) challenges, best practices, and experiences regarding project implementation are documented from the project start onwards and will provide valuable lessons to maximize the impact of future similar projects on EU and national level.

Within the theoretical literature on these subjects, monitoring and evaluation are closely linked and not always distinguished carefully. Generally, the term **monitoring** denotes an activity exercised regularly, routinely, and repeatedly. Monitoring is done over time and usually adheres to clear and transparent criteria. Its primary aim is to identify potential points of improvement or adaptation within the project work (cf. DeGEval – Gesellschaft für Evaluation 2017: 55; 66; 68). As defined for the context of EU Horizon projects, “[monitoring] generates data on an intervention’s *activity and impact over time* in a *continuous* and *systematic* way. It helps identify and address any *implementation problems* of an intervention at the same time as it *generates factual data for future evaluation and impact assessment*” (European Commission 2015: 5, emphasis added).

The term **evaluation**, on the other hand, denominates the systematic examination of the quality, effectiveness, and usefulness of the evaluated object on the basis of empirical data.

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It looks at “*what* has happened, *why* something has occurred and in particular *how much has changed* as a consequence” (European Commission 2015: 5, emphasis added). Like monitoring, evaluation is conducted on the basis of straightforward and transparent criteria. It is directed towards a clearly-defined purpose: This might be a general hindsight assessment of the success of the project (‘did the program work?’), but it can also come in the form of a ‘process evaluation’ which examines an intervention while it is being implemented (cf. Saunders 2016). The information provided by evaluations should be “credible and useful, enabling the incorporation of lessons learned into the decision-making process” (OECD-DAC 2013: 4).

The present theoretical framework draws on both concepts, monitoring and evaluation, adjusting them to the project-specific context and fusing them into a single strategy of monitoring and evaluation. As DISTENDER’s project monitoring workstream is explicitly concerned with ‘impact monitoring’, aspects of both monitoring and evaluation activities are salient to the work conducted: The quantification and maximization of the project’s impacts requires a combination of empirical observation and interpretative-evaluative assessment on the basis of both quantitative and qualitative data. As elaborated in further detail below, impacts rarely materialize within timeframes corresponding to the duration of projects, but tend to become visible – and, thus, measurable – only well after project end. Nevertheless, the required work for maximal impact is performed during the project duration and not afterwards.

To account for this logic, the monitoring workstream of the DISTENDER project will apply a ‘**formative**’ model of integrated monitoring and evaluation to support the project team in steering their work toward optimal impact (cf. DeGEval – Gesellschaft für Evaluation 2017: 27). Contrary to ‘**summative**’ evaluations which are usually conducted after an intervention has been completed, formative evaluations conceptualize ongoing monitoring as part of the active project work. Throughout the DISTENDER runtime, project outcomes and impacts, and their development over time, will be assessed. This will help gauge the extent to which the project is on track to achieve its objectives, as well as allow for an approximate appraisal of the general effectiveness of the interventions and solutions proposed and implemented throughout the project. Based on this, the monitoring team will provide recommendations on how the project objectives can be achieved in the best suitable way. In other words, the monitoring team will at the same time keep the desired long-term impacts of the projects in focus, *as well as* the preconditions for their eventual attainment.

Having defined the activity to be conducted within the project monitoring work package (WP10), as a next step the tools and objects of the activity and how they interact with one another from a theoretical point of view will be clarified. To this purpose, the following section outlines a basic impact pathway, defines its key components, and transposes it to the specific context of the DISTENDER project in the form of a theory of change. Additionally, the concept of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) within the context of large research projects is introduced and linked to the idea of impact monitoring. The second and third chapter of the report then spell out the specific DISTENDER KPIs and give instructions regarding their measurement and appraisal in the future.

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2.2 The impact pathway and definitions of key terms

The DISTENDER monitoring team has developed an *ex-ante* theory of change to conceptualize how change at the level of the target groups and society at large is expected to be triggered by the project work. This is distinct from an *ex-post* theory of change: In developing an *ex-post* theory of change, evaluators retrace how change actually *did* happen as a consequence of the intervention (cf. Mayne 2015: 128; for an example of the *ex-post* approach, see Mezzasalma and Rossignoli 2014).

A theory of change is a framework to show *how* and *why* desired change is expected to happen in a particular situation.¹ It aims to explain how activities contribute to the achievement of results which in turn produce the final intended impacts. Theories of change are useful models for managing and understanding complex interventions such as large research projects. They usually consist of a series of basic logical steps capturing the progress from the exploitation of a project's resources to the project's ultimate effects (Harries et al. 2014: 5).

The theory of change developed for DISTENDER shows how the project is imagined to achieve its objectives, progressing through a chain of short-, medium-, and long-term outcomes and impacts. Key aspects of the project design enter into the theory of change, such as the project's activities, the project's expected outcomes, the target groups of the activities, and the assumptions made regarding the build-up of capacities, skills, and motivations within these target groups. The core element of the theory of change is an 'impact pathway': The pathway which the DISTENDER theory of change relies on can be regarded as a 'classic' model: It consists of a number of basic interlinking concepts which are used widely within the theoretical literature on impact evaluation and are also employed by the European Commission. The individual elements of the impact pathway relate to different steps of how the planning, implementation, and results of the project are imagined to come together. They are classified as **inputs**, **activities**, **outputs**, **outcomes**, and **impacts**. In the following section, they are defined and connected to the work of the DISTENDER project monitoring team (cf. Table I for an overview).

2.2.1 Theoretical concepts: Inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, impacts

Inputs are the actions, tools, tasks and resources which enter into the project. These typically include money, work hours, or technical equipment. The concept may even be extended to variables such as energy consumed, e.g., in energy-intensive computing processes. Most inputs can be described in monetary terms. The inputs required to implement a project are usually defined in the course of project planning. While certain types of inputs, such as monetary resources, are usually decided upon and fixed before project start, other inputs, such as the precise amounts and quality of the data delivered by data providers during the course of the project, cannot always be anticipated in detail.

¹ Other terms than 'theory of change' are also used, often indiscriminately: E.g., logic model; outcome logic model; impact chain; results chain; results framework; theory of cause; theory of action; program roadmap. For the sake of simplicity, and because of the explicit focus on 'impact', 'impact pathway' and 'theory of change' are the only terms used in this report.

In DISTENDER, inputs include large amounts of data which are to be provided by the case studies; funding for the WP activities, but also for workshop activities and interviews to support co-creation processes; and the computing infrastructure used to run climate models and perform dynamical downscaling.

Activities are the actions undertaken by the researchers and other stakeholders engaged in the project. Activities are intended to utilize the inputs in order to achieve the project's goals and produce results.

In DISTENDER, these include research tasks, stakeholder engagement processes, as well as the internal and external communication of the project team. The specific activities and their order within the project are described by a Gantt chart in the grant agreement.

Outputs are the direct results of a project: The products, services, and goods created or supplied by the project, generally “relat[ing] to the expected deliverables of the intervention” (European Commission 2015: 6). As they are directly produced by the project, outputs happen within the short to medium term after project start. Concrete examples for research projects like DISTENDER are published reports (most of the deliverables are in report form), conducted workshops, or posted online articles.

In the case of DISTENDER, all three of the above categories are outside the scope of WP10 – Project Monitoring. Inputs, activities, and outputs are monitored and reported on by WP1 – Project Monitoring across the tasks T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3. As evident from the DISTENDER theory of change outlined below, in order to assess the impacts of the project, it is sufficient to start at the project outcomes and measure these across stakeholder groups and work packages. A further evaluative element is part of WP9 – Case Studies: In T9.3, specific results realized within the project duration and through the project work will be collected, examined, and discussed with the individual case studies through a participatory process.

Outcomes are the specific and measurable short- to medium-term effects of project activities and outputs. The European Commission defines them as “the expected effects, over the medium term, of projects [...] under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures. This may include the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project's results by direct target groups. Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project” (European Commission 2022: 4). Outcomes are usually thought of as happening on different ‘levels’ (cf. Allen et al. 2017: 958):

- i. On the level of **targeted groups and individuals** (learning; enhanced knowledge; changed behaviour, perceptions, understanding, or attitudes)
- ii. On the level of **capabilities** (skills, practices, problem solving capacities)
- iii. On the level of **conditions** (economic, biophysical, social, legal, ...)

These different levels can in theory be linked to one another as “sequential preconditions”, but do not necessarily form a straightforward causal and temporal chain (Allen et al. 2017: 958). Examples for possible outcomes are manifold. What specifically counts as an outcome is highly dependent on the project design and the objectives which the project sets itself. Relative to project context, possible examples of outcomes are citizens understanding the importance of energy saving-measures (in a project aiming at behavioural changes in energy-saving), policymakers understanding the importance of drought adaptation (e.g., in a

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policy-dialogue project on extreme weather events), or a clearer picture of planning deficits and needs for change in planning law for renewable energies (in a capacity-building project specifically designed to support lawmakers' work with crucial information and understanding).

For the DISTENDER project monitoring, most outcomes measured are situated on the level of targeted groups and individuals, as well as on the level of capabilities. Outcomes on the level of conditions will not be measured directly, but rather through survey and interviews of the target groups, in order to better be able to contextualize changes in conditions within the respective case studies. Accordingly, possible outcomes for DISTENDER are 'enhanced willingness to implement certain measures', 'improved communication between researchers and policymakers', 'instated institutional provisions for the integration of climate adaptation and mitigation'.

Impacts are defined by the European Commission as the "wider societal, economic or environmental cumulative changes over a longer period of time" (European Commission 2015: 6) which the project work contributed to. In the context of development programs, where the concept of impact has high prevalence, impacts have been standardly defined as "positive and negative, primary and secondary long term effects produced by a[n ...] intervention, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended" (OECD-DAC 2013: 3). Sometimes, what are here described as 'impacts' are termed 'long-term outcomes' (e.g., Reinholz and Andrews 2020), but this conflates two distinct ideas and bars evaluators from taking into view larger-scale project effects which go beyond the direct outcomes, as further elaborated below. Several aspects are worth pointing out in respect to the cited definitions of 'impacts':

a) The definitions either implicitly or explicitly include both positive and negative effects of a project's activities. Conceptually, this is necessary, as the term 'impact' itself does not carry an evaluative meaning, but simply denotes the "effect of [an] action" (OED Online 2022). This implies that after having been observed, impacts must also be qualified. Following the example of other EU Horizon projects, such as POCITYF (Grant agreement ID 864400), the main focus of the DISTENDER monitoring framework lies on *positive* impacts, but some specific *negative* impacts potentially arising from individual aspects of the project work are covered by a number of indicators of a dedicated impact dimension on negative impacts (see below 1.4.10). Other potential negative impacts very broadly are covered by the ethics self-assessment to be conducted in WP12 (T12.1) which, among other things, will evaluate whether and ensure that DISTENDER follows the 'Do no harm' principle.

b) The definitions either implicitly or explicitly refrain from demanding that impacts be directly causally attributable to specific activities of the project. This is a common problem in impact evaluation. Even regarding the most well-defined project goals, there usually exists an **attribution gap**, an unaccountable-for step between a project result and an observed long-term societal, economic, or environmental change (Stern et al. 2012: 38). This is because interventions are not conducted in laboratory conditions, but in the real world where an infinity of social, economic, environmental, psychological, and political variables may directly or indirectly influence the reception of project results. This attribution gap may also be encountered in the quantification of outcomes, but it is more distinct in, and a defining feature of, the concept of impacts, because impacts are more wide-ranging, longer-term, and are less closely linked to individual project activities and outputs.

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For example, a more extensive bike lane system (outcome) does not automatically lead to more citizens riding their bikes (impact). Several factors, such as a changed social perception of bike-riding, real and perceived safety, increased knowledge about the specificities of bike traffic routing measures, will have an influence on the extent to which the desired impact is achieved. Projects with a clear impact logic should consider these factors in their work and should monitor their development during implementation. In order to do so in the most successful way, project consortia should consciously and explicitly aim at specified impacts from project start (Harries et al. 2014: 23; Stern et al. 2012: 22 and 45; Funnell and Rogers 2011: 150). Whether or not an impact actually materializes is influenced by the specific nature and quality of project outcomes, but to assume that every impact is mechanistically and definitely caused by a certain number and quality of outcomes, also reproduces an unrealistic idea of how social and political realities work (Woolcock 2009).

c) In the given definitions and elsewhere, impacts are characterized by their temporal component – impacts are effects of interventions which become observable only in the long term, usually at a point in time significantly after project end (cf. Rood et al. 2019: 31). Typical project outcomes like capacity and awareness building require time to be utilized, spread into society, and lead to sustained change. This temporal component, however, is only a sufficient, not a necessary condition for an effect to be classified as an impact. As distinguished from outcomes which are the immediate effects of project work and would thus not include long-term effects, impacts on the other hand can at least in theory also become manifest within a short-term or medium-term timeframe. As an example, imagine a policymaker attending a DISTENDER project workshop, in the process gaining new knowledge about the interrelation between agriculture, climate change, and economics. This knowledge gain at the level of individual people in positions of influence is a direct outcome of the project work. Whether this knowledge is translated into policy, or influences the policy agenda, or plays a role in implementing existing policies, is dependent on a variety of factors, not least the current stage of the policy cycle in the respective administration the policymaker is part of. Assume that the administration is currently in the process of formulating a policy to support the planting of certain crops more suited to the projected climatic conditions of the future (i.e., formulating a climate adaptation policy). As a member of the committee tasked with elaborating the policy, the policymaker may remark that certain crops require considerably larger quantities of fertilizer than others, and that fertilizer production in turn has a significant greenhouse gas-footprint. If this aspect is then, in one way or another, incorporated into the final legal text, the project will have made a short-term impact. As noted in the previous paragraph, however, whether this impact does or does not materialize is highly dependent on external factors and stakeholders which the project itself is not able to exert influence on directly.

Table 2: The steps of the impact pathway

	Definition	Example
Inputs	Actions, tools, tasks, resources which enter into the project	Money, work hours, equipment
Activities	Actions undertaken by those engaged in the project, using the <i>inputs</i> to achieve project aims	Research activities, stakeholder engagement processes, internal and external communication

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Outputs	Direct products, services, goods created or supplied by the project; results of <i>activities</i>	Published reports, workshops, online postings
Outcomes	Specific measurable short- to medium-term effects of project <i>activities</i> and <i>outputs</i>	Knowledge on adaptation measures increased; capacity to initiate co-creation processes learned; formulation of financial regulation modified
Impacts	(Usually longer-term) cumulative changes and effects at the level of the project target groups or beyond; intended or unintended effects beyond the immediate scope of the project activities	Legitimacy of climate change mitigation measures increased; interaction between research disciplines sustainably improved

To conclude, impacts materialize gradually, over time, and are influenced, but not necessarily directly affected, by project activities, outputs, and outcomes. They mostly become empirically observable only after the project or intervention ends. Furthermore, while a project can create impacts on an infinite number of individual aspects of the social and natural world, the largest and most sustained impacts are likely to be achieved in those areas which the project sets as its primary objectives before project start. This notion will be further elaborated below in relation to the DISTENDER impact dimensions (see below 1.4).

2.2.2 The impact pathway

Figure 1 Basic impact pathway (from W.K. Kellogg Foundation 2004: 3)

Based on the definitions given above, the impact pathway follows a simple logic: **From inputs to outputs to outcomes to impacts**. The EU Commission defines a pathway to impact as the “logical steps towards the achievement of the expected impacts of the project over time, in particular beyond the duration of a project. A pathway begins with the projects’ results, to their dissemination, exploitation and communication, contributing to the expected outcomes in the work programme topic, and ultimately to the wider scientific, economic and societal impacts of the work programme destination” (European Commission 2022: 4).²

The outputs of a project are directed at certain project target groups. In this way, first, change is achieved on the level of the project work. This includes all stakeholders of the project: Researchers, policymakers, citizens, the funding agency (in this case the European Commission), the interested public. The outputs of a project (ideally) generate positive outcomes on the level of directly targeted groups, such as improvements in knowledge and understanding, increased interest in a certain topic, more detailed models, or connections made between municipal governments to exchange experiences and best practices.

These outcomes, in themselves, are usually not the ultimate goals of interventions. Large research and development projects aim at long-term impacts and are designed to create benefits for society at large. Accordingly, outcomes aimed at should be chosen in relation to these longer-term goals, or ‘impacts’, which become noticeable (and, thus, measurable) after the project ends.

In the reality of implementation, the pathway from outputs to impacts will rarely be observable as a straight line – even the different outcome-levels (see above 1.2.1) cannot necessarily be understood as immediately consecutive steps. The outcome level of groups or individuals, the level of capabilities, and the level of conditions are in part synchronous, in part form a logical sequence.

As a **general example**, consider the long-term impact ‘increase in citizens commuting by bike’. A project is set up to contribute to this impact. The underlying reasons for aiming at this specific impact can be manifold. They range from a reduction in total emissions, to an increase in citizen wellbeing, or a reduction of the number of cars parked in city centres to free up public space. According to the simple impact pathway, the achievement of this aim will require short- to medium-term outcomes on different levels: On the one hand, it will require policymakers’ comprehensive *understanding* of the issue, as well as their *willingness* to change it. Further, it will require a change in *external conditions* (e.g., infrastructure and policy) such as the transformation of car lanes into bike lanes, tax benefits and employer bonuses for bikes. Another precondition for the desired impact to materialize would be changes in the *attitudes* and *perceptions* of end-users (in this case, citizens commuting to and from work): Cars would need to cease to be symbols of status; biking would need to be perceived as a desirable lifestyle choice, etc. Accordingly, a single longer-term impact requires the combination of multiple outcomes. On the other hand, a single outcome can contribute to multiple impacts: Citizens learning about the environment and health benefits of biking may also adjust other areas of their lifestyles and consumption patterns. To give another example, an infrastructural intervention on bike lanes is likely to decrease the rate of accidents while at the same time increasing the number of people who ride their bicycles.

² Note that in the version depicted here, the pathway does not only begin with the project’s results, but already includes the inputs and activities stage of DISTENDER, as all project activity during the project duration is the area where the project monitoring team will have most influence on (cf. 1.1).

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A project with sufficient resources could theoretically aim to act on all the above levels relevant to the final impact: The project could conduct capacity-building workshops for policy-makers, produce scientific reports on the projected health and urban development benefits of an increase in bike traffic, organize awareness raising campaigns directed at citizens, support the construction of new bicycle infrastructure with technical know-how. Naturally, achieving positive results in all areas would still not guarantee that the increase in biking commuters actually materializes right away, or at any time at all. Still, the extent to which and the way in which these outcomes are fulfilled *will* condition the extent to which the impact itself materializes in the long term. This is the basic assumption of the impact pathway as presented here.

Accordingly, a crucial next step will be the identification of the precise impacts of the DISTENDER project, and the outcomes pertinent to these impacts. These outcomes and impacts are, naturally, dependent on the specific design and activities of the project. This is why the **impact pathway** as described in this chapter is elaborated into a DISTENDER-specific **theory of change** in the following chapters (1.3-1.5).

2.3 Impact multipliers and causal link assumptions

To convert the generic impact framework into a distinct theory of change for the project, the impact pathway must be embedded within the project context. Designing the monitoring and evaluation framework on the basis of the specific characteristics of projects is crucial for effective and purposeful impact evaluation (cf. Rogers 2009: 218f).

For the construction of the DISTENDER KPI framework, a number of initial questions were asked by the monitoring team:

- Which **components or structural elements of the project** will most likely **determine the extent** of the project's impact?
- What **kinds of changes** will the project be able to **deliver for maximal impact**?
- In which broad **thematic areas** will the project most likely **have the largest impact**?

On the basis of these questions, three auxiliary concepts were developed to shape the theory of change and pick appropriate indicators. The first two of these concepts attempt to provide an answer to the first two questions and are treated in this subchapter: 'Impact multipliers' and 'causal link assumptions'. While causal link assumptions help focalize the relevant changes to be monitored, the impact multipliers are those products or target groups of the project which are essential for delivering impact. The third question is tackled by the concept of the 'impact dimensions', which is discussed in the following subchapter (1.4).

2.3.1 Impact multipliers

The concept of impact multipliers was developed for DISTENDER specifically, but similar concepts are prevalent in the literature (e.g., the concept of 'enablers' in Harries et al. 2014; or the concept of 'change agents' in Roberts and Khattri 2012: 23; the concept of 'Critical Success Factors' defined by Parmenter 2020 in a different context is similar, too). Impact

multipliers are understood to be the target groups or products of the project which are particularly crucial for the results of the project to achieve a maximum positive effect. They are identified on the basis of the specific project design.

Whether or not DISTENDER can generate impact hinges to a large degree on these multipliers – each one of them, as an element of the project, represents both an opportunity and a challenge for the whole project. The monitoring team has identified three impact multipliers for DISTENDER: The *researchers*, on the one hand, the *stakeholders of the case studies*, on the other hand, as well as the *Decision Support System (DSS)* which will be the central product of the project work. The multipliers interlink with one another, in that throughout the project duration, cross-cutting communication and collaboration takes place between the researchers, between the stakeholders of the case studies, and between researchers and stakeholders of the case studies. The final DSS, then, will serve as both a product of this communication and collaboration, as well as a facilitator of it in the future, and a dissemination device for the scientific results of the project work.

a) **Researchers.** First, the research team itself can serve as an impact booster. The DISTENDER research consortium is international and interdisciplinary to a very high degree. The project facilitates collaboration between experts in climate modelling, socioeconomic modelling, and sector-specific modelling. It brings together IT specialists, policy researchers and natural scientists to work together on a single product. The exchange with scientists from other EU-funded research projects will further help proliferate DISTENDER's impacts throughout the European research community. For the global and multi-faceted challenge of climate change, this constellation represents an opportunity; within the course of implementing the project, it may also turn out to be a challenge. Problems in communication and mutual understanding must be identified and addressed early on as not to hinder the project progress. This is why the impact monitoring will devote special attention to the interaction of the project researchers amongst each other and with other stakeholders, and conduct regular surveys and assessments among them.

b) **Case studies and external stakeholders.** Another impact multiplier of DISTENDER is the large inter-European and diverse group of pilot-study stakeholders which the project is addressing and working together with. Involvement of and communication with these stakeholders facilitates direct local implementation of project results, and can boost awareness and knowledge about complex issues relating to climate change across the target group. If done wrong, however, stakeholder involvement can also lead to disillusionment and inaction (cf. Reed 2008). Again, this impact multiplier comes with both potentials and pitfalls. DISTENDER is a highly specialized and technical research project, so that in order to be impact multipliers proper, the stakeholders from the project's case studies must have a specialized background and possess pre-existing knowledge on the action fields touched by the project, such as climate adaptation policy, or land-use planning. Stakeholders with this kind of specialist knowledge are the most appropriate target group of the project. This does not mean that the general public should not also be considered in the impact evaluation, and it is included in the DISTENDER KPI framework. However, the general public is not regarded as a DISTENDER impact multiplier. Apart from the pre-existing technical knowledge, the internal and external project stakeholders from the case studies ideally have significant influence within their respective domains. The case study stakeholders which DISTENDER engages, such as Hanze University of Applied Sciences (HUAS) from the Netherlands case study, represent the connection between technical knowledge and local application and practical

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action through policymaking. Therefore, the role of the case study stakeholders is fundamental to spread the knowledge generated by DISTENDER and put it into concrete action at local scale.

c) **Decision Support System (DSS)**. Apart from the researchers and the case study representatives, the primary multiplier of DISTENDER's impact will be the Decision Support System developed on the basis of the modelling results, the developed scenarios, and the designed strategies. The DSS will translate the scientific results of the project into policy-relevant decisions and into concrete paths of action to be implemented at local level. Ensuring that the development and implementation of the DSS goes well is one chief focus of the DISTENDER monitoring framework: Different groups of stakeholders are positioned at different ends of the DSS. While the researchers must order and present their work in a format which the DSS will be able to process, the recommendations given by the DSS must come in a comprehensible and intuitive format so that decisionmakers from the case studies are able to work with the results. In this way, much of the success and impact of DISTENDER hinges on whether the DSS fulfils the expectations, needs, demands, and requirements of stakeholders of the case studies and the scientists. The DSS, too, can turn out to be both an impact multiplier and impact divisor: When Decision Support Systems do not deliver utilizable or comprehensible recommendations, or their purpose, their potentials and limitations are not communicated and understood in advance, they may in fact become counterproductive for increasing willingness and capacity of stakeholders to implement ambitious climate action (see the early examples from Cox 1996, more recently Arnott and Dodson 2008).

It is important to stress that the concept of the impact multipliers is distinct from the theoretical elements of the impact pathway: Neither are the researchers and the case study stakeholders simply the 'target groups' of the DISTENDER project, nor is the DSS just one of its outputs. The impact multipliers have been chosen for their special significance for impactful project work. The outcome indicators defined in chapters 2 and 3 take into account this fact and are derived from these three focal areas of DISTENDER. The causal link assumptions, defined and illustrated by examples in the following section, are another foundation for the outcomes picked by the monitoring team.

2.3.2 Causal link assumptions

The concept of causal link assumptions refers to the causal links between the project activities and its impact. More precisely, they specify *how* and *why* the project team expects the outputs of the project to lead to positive outcomes and, eventually, positive impact. Clearly, there may be other factors influencing the impacts of DISTENDER, but for the sake of practicability and simplicity, three broad areas have been specified (adapted from Mayne 2015). The assumptions which the monitoring team deems relevant for DISTENDER concern 'reach', 'capacity change', and 'behaviour change'. These are assumptions about the need for results of the project to *reach* the target group, to change their *knowledge, skills, and opportunities*, and to change their *actual behaviour and practices*.

a) **Reach assumptions** refer to engagement moments, events, and conditions which need to be in place so that project outputs actually reach the project's target groups and are positively received by them. This requires that the specific groups targeted are the 'right' groups which the outputs should be addressed to. It also implies that the project should aim at

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reaching groups beyond those who self-select to be part of the project, and consider potential stakeholders beyond those already engaged in the project work directly (Mayne 2015: 124).

b) **Capacity change assumptions** refer to project outcomes regarding improved knowledge, skills, and opportunities of the project target groups. In order for this to support the selection of salient outcomes, the most relevant capacities for the achievement of the project objectives need to be identified in advance (Mayne 2015: 124). In the case of DISTENDER, this was done in collaboration with the experts from the respective work packages (cf. 2.2).

c) **Behaviour change assumptions** refer to project outcomes regarding actual changes in target group practice and behaviour. Crucial preconditions for behaviour change are financial capacities, willingness and motivation for implementing practices, the political and policy frameworks, and an acceptance across the board of problems and related methods to solve them (Mayne 2015: 124f).

While these assumptions are spelled out explicitly here for the purpose of impact monitoring, they often already enter into the design stage of the project implicitly. Within DISTENDER, for example, a whole work package is dedicated to the communication and exploitation of results to ensure that these results reach the most critical audiences for proliferation and maximal impact. Equally, it is assumed that certain types of stakeholders should be addressed and included in the co-creation processes of the project, to a) maximize the knowledge created, and b) provide knowledge to those who are actually in the position to use it. Thirdly, and most importantly, the project consortium consists of both scientists with diverse backgrounds and policy practitioners from across Europe to work together and create new practical and action-guiding knowledge which will be utilized to improve climate policy and climate action.

The three kinds of causal link assumptions inform the outcomes which will be measured by the monitoring team. They are the reason why the Key Performance Indicators developed in this framework chiefly measure changes like ‘attained knowledge’, ‘willingness to change behaviour’, ‘newly adopted practices’, or ‘response rate’ and ‘outreach’ (also see chapters 2 and 3). The following table provides some examples for the kinds of specific outcomes expected on the basis of the respective causal link assumptions.

Table 3: Causal link assumptions for DISTENDER

	Examples of outcomes for DISTENDER
Reach assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lasting networks are established • Diverse stakeholder groups are engaged • Diverse engagement platforms are created or used • Core stakeholders’ engagement is stable and continuous • Non-financial stakeholders are involved in cost-benefit analyses
Capacity change assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops are of good quality • Guidelines for interpreting scenarios are comprehensible for target groups

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers understand potential conflicts between mitigation and adaptation strategies • Communication and collaboration between climate, socioeconomic, and impact modellers are improved • Communication and collaboration between policymakers and scientists are improved
Behavioural change assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders have a sense of ownership of the (interim) project results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders feel involved in climate change challenges • Stakeholders are willing to fund climate change action • Scenarios developed can be easily integrated into existing strategies • Scientific results can be easily integrated into framework (EU) policy

2.4 DISTENDER objectives and impact dimensions

The answer to the final question posed above in 1.3 ('In which broad thematic areas will the project most likely have the largest impact?') will focalize the impact monitoring on those fields of action most engaged in by the project consortium. Due to the wide thematic focus of DISTENDER, finding a utilizable answer to this question is hard: DISTENDER addresses the capacity of European cities and communities to cope with the causes and effects of climate change and aims to strengthen their resilience in the face of the challenges of the future generally. It does so by a combination of climate science and geography, socioeconomics, political science, and policy consulting. The specific combination of multiple disciplines and methodological approaches in DISTENDER was chosen to do justice to the complex nature of the phenomenon of climate change and its impacts on European society. In combination, the individual elements of DISTENDER come together to form a project which is both unique and innovative. The most central elements of DISTENDER's uniqueness are captured by the project **objectives** which were defined at the outset of the project (Table 3). All of these objectives work towards impact in the broader areas of climate resilience, climate mitigation, and climate adaptation, but each does so in its own specific and innovative way. The objectives specify the distinctive and unique contributions that the DISTENDER team, with its interdisciplinary and diverse make-up hopes to achieve in the fight against climate change. The objectives themselves derive from the original call by the European Union and thus represent some of the central desirables for climate action on the levels of governance, society, and the economy, as seen by the EU Commission.

To integrate the project objectives into the project's theory of change, the objectives were analysed and boiled down to their core elements. "Working backwards" in this way, 10 '**impact dimensions**' were created (Roberts and Khattri 2012: 14). The concept of 'dimensions' is common in the development of methodological frameworks for performance and impact measurement: Alternative labels used elsewhere include 'domains', 'layers', or 'themes' for indicator grouping (cf. Angelakoglu et al. 2019: 277; Hara et al. 2016: 4; Siddall et al. 2013: 89). The dimensions chosen for DISTENDER are very specific to the layout of the project, but as part of a theoretical framework, the concept of 'dimensions' could be adapted easily for projects with a different thematic focus. Some of the dimensions are pertinent with the participatory process which will characterize DISTENDER, whereas others focus more on the technical side of the development of models and scenarios. The dimensions were chosen to encompass all the phases and aspects of the project.

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Within the formal design of DISTENDER, the project objectives are explicitly linked to distinct work packages responsible for their achievement. The monitoring approach outlined in this report moves away from this compartmentalization of objectives by work packages. The project, as designed, is integrated to a high degree: All work packages are strongly connected with and dependent on the work done in other work packages. The move from work-package-specific objectives to overarching impact dimensions is intended to do justice to this holistic nature of the project and to encourage all work packages of the project to work towards common goals. This does not imply that all work packages will achieve equal impact on all dimensions, but it serves to ensure that all potential impacts of DISTENDER will be considered within the activities conducted of each individual work package.

Table 4: Detailed list of DISTENDER objectives

	Title	Detailed description
Objective 1	Stakeholder engagement process & participation using co-creation	Different target groups (at least 5) will be involved to address the requirements for a wide range of stakeholders within selected case studies. The stakeholder-driven methodology will be applied for creating socio-economic, integrated strategies and discovering synergies and trade-offs of the adaptation and mitigation strategies.
Objective 2	Participatory development of localized socio-economic scenarios	A set of local socio-economic scenarios will be developed by stakeholders, facilitated by the combination of bottom-up participatory methodology in combination with top-down approaches. Resulting scenarios are locally useful and comprehensive, while consistent with the global and Europe SSPs. A specific aim is to extend and improve the European SSPs by considering new SSPs and novel elements related to non-linearities and surprises. These socio-economic futures will be integrated with climate storylines and projections, adaptation and mitigation, and vulnerability strategies, by combining the state-of-the-art scenario framework and methodology (e.g., Story and Simulation approach). Particular attention will be devoted to vulnerable categories inclusion and avoiding the gender gap.
Objective 3	Produce localized climate storylines through a downscaling framework	Apply transferable modelling tools to deliver high resolution data (up to meters) of micro-climatic, atmospheric and environmental stressors to enhance the prediction capacity for risk and vulnerability assessment.
Objective 4	Risk and vulnerability assessment based on a set of bio-physical, social and economic indicators produced by a wide range of multi-scale and cross-sectorial models	This analysis serves as a starting point for developing adaptation and mitigation strategies in an integrated way for different stakeholders, assets and sectors (health and well-being, energy, water, transport, agroforestry and biodiversity). In each of the case studies, an adequate set of indicators (around 20-30) will be tested.
Objective 5	Robust adaptation and mitigation actions and	The project will work with stakeholders to develop visions of their ideal future and work backwards from these taking into

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	policies from a suite of harmonized strategies constructed through participatory methods	consideration the opportunities and constraints when combining adaptation and mitigation options from existing policy and practice. Resulting strategies will be confronted with the sets of scenarios to identify those actions that would work across all different scenarios, resulting in robust actions.
Objective 6	Sectoral, integrated and economy-wide economic evaluation of climate strategies	Through multi-scale and cross-sectorial computable general equilibrium model using inputs from the DISTENDER sectorial impacts assessment models. A holistic evaluation will enable the identification of innovative and participative business and finance models and enabling the involvement of new stakeholders.
Objective 7	Translate scientific results into policy relevant actions	Develop a dynamic and flexible Decision Support System (DSS) which will integrate the outcomes of the other objectives and will allow future stakeholders to assess climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies over different sectors concerning changes of environmental and socio-economic conditions during the next decades. The DSS will help to find the optimal strategies by applying a multi-criteria approach by appraising tailored options (addressing effectiveness, feasibility, affordability, etc.) and prioritizing actions to best allocate funds.
Objective 8	Testing and replication of the outcomes of the project through case studies	The test cases will cover different climatic zones, scales and political sectors improving the knowledge about trade-offs and synergies between mitigation and adaptation. The case study demonstrators shall ensure the replicability of the developed tools and processes beyond the lifetime of the DISTENDER and upscale case-study scenarios to improve the current set of European and global SSPs.
Objective 9	Network to promote and exchange the outputs of the projects with other EU and international initiatives about climate change	DISTENDER will define a plan to broaden the networks and their engagement with actions to identify, contact and establish lasting relationships over time at local, regional, national and international levels, as to identify collaboration opportunities, new agreements and collaborative research with specific interest in the sister projects of this call, cluster 4 and cluster 6. Collaboration among Working Groups I, II, and III of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change will be facilitated and enhanced.

On the basis of these nine objectives, ten impact dimensions were chosen: Co-creation; Participation; Network; Science-policy/science-science interactions; Awareness and understanding of climate change issues; Implementation; Cost-efficiency; Integration of adaptation and mitigation; Cross-sector and multi-scale; Negative impacts. The tenth dimension, relating to negative impacts, does not derive directly from the objectives and overarches all core themes which the project touches upon. Unlike the other dimensions, it is *not* theme-specific. In the following, each dimension is argued for on the basis of the list of objectives, as well as a defined as precisely as is possible at this early stage. For the definitions, relevant peer-reviewed and 'grey' literature stemming from similar projects was scanned. The ordering of the dimension is without meaning – it merely takes a rough cue from the ordering of the objectives in the initial objectives list.

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2.4.1 Co-creation

The challenges posed by climate change are experienced and dealt with differently across society. They may be further amplified when affected actors have differing or even contrary perspectives on the problem, and when access to resources and political power to deal with the risks and opportunities arising from climate change are distributed unequally. Newly developed strategies to cope with these challenges also affect and benefit people in different ways, depending on their position within society. Since climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies, as well as socioeconomic scenarios, often concern action at local and regional scale, it is pivotal to find a working method which includes as many perspectives as possible in the collaborative development of these strategies and scenarios, in order to produce superior solutions.

The method of “co-creation”³ offers a promising approach to the problem posed: If done well, co-creation is capable of including a variety of stakeholder perspectives and can provide an equal footing regarding knowledge and potential contribution. It also dedicates special attention to the identification of the needs and capacities of individual stakeholders to deal with the challenges to be tackled. In this way, the method of co-creation may equip stakeholders with the motivation and the right tools to come up with solutions collaboratively. Co-creation attempts to steer clear of largely science-driven top-down approaches to climate change adaptation and mitigation, and performs a shift towards a combination of top-down and bottom-up elements in the design of scenarios, usability of data, and creation of strategies (Chapman et al. 2018: 17).

Although definitions of co-creation vary across the literature, earlier co-creation-focused EU Horizon 2020 projects have outlined the method in its basic elements. According to this previous work, defining characteristics of co-creation are its transdisciplinary form of knowledge production, the enabling of mutual learning between different organisations, an emphasis on equality, trust, and accountability, and the varying degrees of ownership by those involved in the co-creation processes over its products (Chapman 2018: 18f, also cf. Fagiewicz et al. 2021).

The strong co-creation element of the DISTENDER project is also the reason for labelling one of the impact dimensions ‘Co-creation’. The dimension originates from the first three objectives, especially Objective 1 which states that DISTENDER’s participatory processes will employ co-creation techniques, rather than other techniques for participatory work (e.g., simple ‘voting’, or top-down capacity building). The dimension is understood to only cover impacts deriving from the application of the co-creation *method*; accordingly, the thrust of this dimension is *empirical*, rather than *normative* (for the normative component of participatory processes more broadly, see 1.4.2 on the ‘Participation’ dimension). The method is assumed to be selected because it produces objectively better results than top-down approaches, and not because it is normatively desirable over such approaches.

Within the project, the co-creation facilitation and implementation are managed by WP2 – Co-creation & stakeholder engagement. Stakeholder diversity and representation are key to the co-creation within DISTENDER, together with stakeholders’ motivation, interest and sat-

³ Associated terms used throughout the literature are ‘co-design’ and ‘co-development’.

isfaction. In the monitoring framework, observer assessments of how the co-creation process is going are interlinked with subjective responses in order to identify strengths, criticalities and barriers within the implementation of the co-creation method from all sides.

2.4.2 Participation

The impact dimension of ‘Participation’ is linked to the co-creation method in practice, but separated from it within this theoretical framework. Like ‘Co-creation’, ‘Participation’, too, aims at involving heterogeneous actors to produce results: Citizen and industry associations, laypeople, and decision-makers have for some time been considered as an integral and active component of large research projects (Scherhauer 2021; Brandsen et al. 2018: 6). While co-creation is gaining prevalence as a form of participatory governance, it is not the only possible participatory approach to research-driven strategy development (cf. Røiseland 2022: 1494). To distinguish the practical aspects of the particular method chosen for DISTENDER from the realization of the normative core of participatory action, which are central to the project as designed, this separate impact dimension was created (for a discussion of the conceptual distinction between co-creation and participation and its practical implications, see Lund 2018).

The central normative reason for including participatory elements within a project like DISTENDER is to increase the legitimacy of results and of the strategies developed (Røiseland 2022). Democratic legitimacy, on one reading of the concept, requires stakeholders to feel that decisions made within democratic systems are acceptable to them (Beetham 1991). Accordingly, actively involving a representative part of the population in the core steps of the project plan is intended to foster a sense of ownership regarding the results of the project. On a slightly different reading, democratic legitimacy requires equal opportunity for involvement in the decision-making process of all groups and individuals affected by a decision (here, the focus is on *procedure*, see Peter 2009: 75). While the first rendition of the concept is subjective in that it draws on the experience of the individuals involved, the latter understanding requires an objective observer to assess the extent to which equal access and a just distribution of influence were guaranteed in the participation process. Accordingly, the relationship between stakeholders in participatory processes should be based on the idea of balanced influence regarding their positions within the decision-making process (Chaudhary et al. 2018). Under-representation, power asymmetries and inequalities are likely to threaten the success of participatory processes (Barnaud et al. 2018).

Thus, their successful participatory involvement may increase stakeholders’ buy-in, as well as the legitimacy of the solutions developed. Methods for improving participation, like stakeholder analysis, help to build trust, bring in additional expertise, and close accountability gaps (Transparency International 2011). In relation to climate change, successful participation has three interconnected elements: Access to information, which allows for sharing opinions and research results; direct engagement, which gives stakeholders a chance to influence policy; and oversight, which allows stakeholders to assess and evaluate the implemented strategies. Different international entities, such as the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC 2015) use participation in their scoping and screening phases to reduce fragmentation and a sense of alienation from projects’ outcomes.

In the DISTENDER monitoring framework, the participation dimension tackles the experience of the stakeholders engaged in the participatory process. These tools are followed by

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subjective indicators, such as ‘sense of ownership’, ‘involvement’ and ‘satisfaction’ regarding services provided by the project to cross-verify the degree of participation in the process.

2.4.3 Network

Conceptually, the ‘Network’ dimension is connected to the two previous dimensions ‘Co-creation’ and ‘Participation’, in that it is concerned with the involvement and integration of a multiplicity and variety of actors in climate policymaking. While ‘Co-creation’ aims at the implementation of a method, and ‘Participation’ at certain normative requirements, ‘Network’ is directed at lasting structural elements resulting from the DISTENDER project.

From a sociological perspective, networks are systems of multiple interacting elements, embedded within institutional, social, and political contexts. The nodes in a network can consist of individual actors connected to one another, of institutions or government departments, or whole societal areas mutually interrelated, such as ‘climate science’ and ‘the private sector’ (Tsonis et al. 2006). These nodes, and the power relations between them, shape both project processes and outputs; furthermore, they shape actors’ and institutions’ preferences and motivations and allow for the establishment of continuous flows of experiences and knowledges between the nodes (Ingold 2011). The importance of networks for achieving common objectives and delivering shared results is widely acknowledged in the literature. Apart from achieving better results, networks between government, science, and civil society actors in particular strengthen coordination and efficiency on all levels of governance.

Climate adaptation and mitigation strategies work on multiple levels and are advanced by a multiplicity of actors (Wurzel et al. 2019). The number of formalized networks in climate projects has increased over the last decade, resulting in increased coordination, sharing of information and an intensified exchange of experiences (Acuto and Leffel, 2020). For example, showcase initiatives like the ‘100 climate-neutral cities by 2030’ initiative⁴, networks of international actors (e.g., [The Covenant of Mayors](#)), or even social movements such as Friday for Future have all emerged over the last decade and can be considered to profit from their strong network (United Nations, n.d.). However, in climate strategies, one of the main barriers is the lack of communication between different levels of a network which consequently may lead to stagnation in terms of implementation and concrete results (Bhavani and Kashmeera, 2022). The identification of both potential and already-existing coherent and stable networks is therefore required to avoid short-lasting communicative structures.

Following these considerations, DISTENDER focuses on networks between internal project’s participants, science, governments and civil society. For example, the project will assess potential exchange of practices between case studies. Generally, in the ‘Network’ dimension lasting structures springing (at least partly) from the activities of DISTENDER are monitored from an early stage onward. Most of the impact generated on this dimension will become visible only after project end, but the aim of the monitoring activity is to support DISTENDER stakeholders in identifying potential networks at an early stage and proactively encourage their formation. The KPIs developed on this dimension complement each other to assess the structure and effectiveness of network creation from the perspectives of actors involved in networks and of impartial observers. Specifically, the number of networks formed is cross-verified with the quality of interdisciplinary cooperation and the level of connections made among stakeholders for sharing experiences and knowledge. To the extent possible,

⁴ [Climate-neutral and smart cities \(europa.eu\)](#)

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the evaluation of networks also highlights potential conflicts and barriers affecting the networking activity. To this end, quantitative tools are combined with qualitative analysis to identify the source of conflicts and possible solutions to overcome them. Moreover, as cross-level power imbalances influence communication and collaboration across multiple levels (Di Gregorio et al. 2019), DISTENDER will take them into account together with the nature of the interactions between stakeholders.

2.4.4 Science-policy and science-science interaction

The ‘Science-policy and science-science interaction’ dimensions refers to the bidirectional exchange between policymakers (e.g., within municipal governments) and scientists (e.g., climate modellers), as well as the bidirectional exchange between scientists and scientists within the project and throughout the scientific community more widely. The United Nations Development Programme describes the interaction between science and policy as an exchange of knowledge, data, information and experience between actors from both sides and emphasises the importance of this interaction for achieving climate goals (UNDP 2020). It is accepted that science can inform policy, and that policies should direct science towards more equal, data-based and greater information. Besides, scientific output needs to be continuously adapted and up-to-date to social, regulatory, and political changes. Therefore, interaction between policy and science should be combined with a flexible approach able to change the shape of interaction after potential changes. Empirical research shows that scientific output deriving from the collaboration between scientists and policymakers is more reliable and utilizable for supporting decisions and solving concrete problems because the collaborative process, if successful, helps align what policy wants with what science has to offer (McKinley et al. 2012). Beyond creating more usable and reliable knowledge, these interactions may “open up a dialogue between science and society” which may work towards preventing both the “politicization of science and the scientization of policy” (Kirchhoff et al. 2015, also cf. Gough 2003). Moreover, science-science interaction is relevant to create a comprehensible and holistic framework. Indeed, science is not a homogenous box of information. Different types of sciences have different technologies, tools, approaches towards research and perspectives which require a clear communication and the overcome of barriers which can limit the inflow of information (Michael 1992). As such, cross-interaction of knowledge and shared information is fundamental to create a science-science dimension.

In the context of climate change, a cross-cutting global issue which can be understood and dealt with only through an integrated approach and strong cooperation between scientists and policymakers, it is crucial that a) scientists understand the needs, options, possibilities, and challenges of policymakers when it comes to turning scientific results into concrete measures; and that b) policymakers understand the potential contributions and limitations of science to policymaking. Communication between the two areas must work smoothly – both in the context of DISTENDER and the fight against climate change generally. The same is true of communication between scientific disciplines who must complement and support one another. The monitoring of the ‘Science-policy/science-science interaction’ dimension also explicitly takes into account the disciplinary diversity and transdisciplinarity of the project. The selection of indicators aims at improving communication, identifying uncertainties and barriers that divide science and policy and scientists from different disciplines, and creating and utilizing a common language. Furthermore, the developed indicators serve to grasp the understanding of scientific methods by policymakers and of stakeholder requirements by scientists to create the basis for utilizing scientific results in climate policy design.

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For example, a holistic understanding of methodological barriers in modelling and scenario analysis is likely to highlight project's potentialities as well as potential criticalities when these methods are applied in the field. Science-science interactions further the learning process between the project's experts, particularly regarding downscaling techniques and the co-design of climatic indicators.

2.4.5 Awareness and understanding of climate change issues

The impact dimension 'Awareness and understanding' concerns the knowledge generation and distribution effected by the DISTENDER project throughout all target groups. As stated by the World Health Organization, awareness and understanding of the effects of climate change facilitate greater innovation in project development and societal support for the actions needed to reduce the multi-dimensional impacts of climate change. Awareness about existing measures and prevalent vulnerabilities might not be equally spread across society or even among all direct stakeholders of a project. This dimension is a fundamental component of climate processes to enhance resilience at different levels and systems, increase enthusiasm and support, stimulate self-awareness, and, additionally, mobilise local knowledge and resources (Khatibi et al. 2021).

Awareness of the causes and effects of climate change is a core component of climate policies in order to sensitize the population about climate vulnerabilities and inform citizens about sustainable lifestyles and behaviour. The concept is strictly interrelated with an understanding of climate change issues; awareness is more emotional and influenced by external as well as internal factors. A thorough understanding on climate change issues does not automatically lead to a high sense of awareness or vice versa. Therefore, these two concepts, even if strongly interlinked, are usually separated as two different items in climate change projects.

The cross-cutting nature of climate change, and its effects on all layers of society and all citizens, makes an impact on citizens' awareness highly desirable for DISTENDER. Boosting awareness of DISTENDER's specific contributions to solving climate challenges will also lead to a higher impact of the project on other societal levels and impact dimensions. First and foremost, the desire to achieve increased awareness calls for effective communication and dissemination practices which need to be audience oriented, transparent, inclusive and accessible. Besides, in DISTENDER, the 'Awareness and understanding' dimension stresses the importance of novel concepts which are first understood and then adopted by stakeholders. An in-depth understanding of differences and elements that interlink climate adaptation and mitigation issues, and consequently their representation, is another aspect covered by the project. Also, awareness and understanding of uncertainties and vulnerabilities are part of this dimension. In DISTENDER, the aim of awareness differs between contexts/work packages but generally includes increased concern, informing the targeted audience and creating a positive picture of the outcomes.

2.4.6 Implementation

Understanding and awareness might further the concrete implementation of strategies and actions. In order to move from strategic action plans to concrete implementation, the development of a string of concrete actions and an assessment of their feasibility is required. DISTENDER's outcomes may serve as basis for the implementation of climate change

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measures, in that the project design already contains the shift from knowledge about and understanding of climate change, towards the elaboration and execution of actual measures within societies. One thrust of the 'Implementation' dimension thus is to determine the processes which lead mitigation and adaptation measures towards successful delivery. Implementation may also imply the downscaling of national- or provincial-level strategies to a lower level of governance and the transfer of concrete measures to different action contexts (e.g. national energy strategies at a local scale should consider the natural sources of energy available in the area). Resources to be specified in the implementation planning are required to successfully execute measures. In this sense, implementation requires a feasibility assessment that considers a clearly-defined group of stakeholders and their available resources. These resources might include stakeholders' financial capacity, knowledge and expertise, values, time availability, and the specific tools and methods at hand. Streamlining governance and decision-making processes among stakeholders is a cornerstone in promoting the transition from planning to the implementation of adaptation and mitigation (Mimura et al. 2014).

As for DISTENDER, implementation refers to impacts in the context of locally implemented adaptation and mitigation measures, primarily in the core case studies and those further European cities and municipalities following the progress of the project as observers. By facilitating decision-making processes about concrete measures, and supplementing these with scientific insights, DISTENDER will have significant impact. Specifically, transferability of knowledge, tools, and results are considered by the KPIs in the 'Implementation' dimension. The project will be implemented using an audience targeted approach to adaptation and mitigation and will incorporate the perspectives of different stakeholders involved. Besides, the 'Implementation' dimension targets different levels of applicability, such as multi-scale governance, conflicting and potentially synergistic legislative and regulatory rules, as well as locally utilizable climate impact assessments and climate scenarios. Furthermore, DISTENDER works in the reproducibility of strategies beyond case studies, thus, transferring the projects' results and methods outside the scope of the project.

2.4.7 Cost-efficiency

Risks arising from climate change vary significantly in their nature and severity, as well as their predictability and the frequency within which they may potentially arise. Sound and integrated economic analysis and advice can offer valuable support to decisionmakers in their efforts to integrate climate risk analysis into strategies. This advice usually comes in the form of a quantification of the costs and benefits linked to projected action and inaction, respectively (OECD 2015).

By integrating various stakeholders from many different sectors, DISTENDER can further the prevalence of cost-efficiency analyses across sectors and motivate stakeholders to collect data on adaptation and mitigation costs and benefits and integrate it into their planning. The multi-disciplinary approach of DISTENDER also promises to open up new methodological lanes for the maximization of benefits and the minimization of costs. In the long run, increased cost-efficiency is expected to serve as a booster for local implementation: If robust adaptation and mitigation strategies can be demonstrated to offer significant advantages in terms of cost-efficiency over other, less climate-focused, strategies, these strategies are more likely to be implemented.

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While developing scientifically sound mitigative and adaptive measures against climate change, the DISTENDER project also supports the development of market-viable solutions and aims to improve the performance of climate change solutions in terms of profitability. In WP7, cost-benefit analyses will be employed to assess the monetary benefits across different sectors. Extensive scientific cost-benefit analyses for climate change adaptation measures are readily available, but still suffer from the limited availability of specified data (see, e.g., Tröltzsch et al. 2012). Apart from contributing to the proliferation of active data collection at all scales of governance and society, the uptake of cost-benefit analyses for policymaking and strategy design is a potential to be unlocked by the project for other purposes as well: In the context of DISTENDER, cost-benefit analyses will increase the capacity of all stakeholders to make decisions in their own best interests. Additionally, quantification of investment benefits and vulnerability costs over the long term will increase stakeholders' motivation generally to redirect funding to adaptation and mitigation measures.

2.4.8 Integration of adaptation and mitigation

The dimension 'Integration of adaptation and mitigation' is directed at DISTENDER's core field of intended impact, the integration of adaptive and mitigative measures in the fight against climate change: This integration implies an identification of potential trade-offs, a reduction of conflicts, as well as an increase in synergies between the two policy fields (Grafakos et al. 2018).

An in-depth understanding of the consequences and most important benefits of mitigation and adaptation, respectively, within the context of a single project may generate innovative and previously untapped approaches to considering these fields in unison. For example, indicators focussing on the concept of 'trade-offs' might lead to a better understanding of dynamics among different stakeholders, their interest, resulting in the delivery of more inclusive and accessible outcomes. Even though mitigation and adaptation strategies might follow different paths for implementation, drivers of mitigation and adaptation are usually common, and solutions can be interrelated. A broad-scale and holistic analysis can tackle these drivers and strengthen synergies, improve cost-effectiveness, avoid conflicts, and help manage trade-offs (Trisolini 2014).

Aligned with the above-mentioned definition, the 'Integration of climate mitigation and adaptation' dimension refers to the integration of adaptive and mitigative measures through an identification of potential trade-offs and synergies and a maximization of co-benefits between the two fields of policymaking. Specifically, the willingness to develop mitigation and adaptation measures is investigated at a case-study level. DISTENDER strengthens the understanding of the concepts of adaptation, mitigation, trade-offs, synergies and their consequent vulnerabilities by a holistic, systems-based analysis that considers the quantitative and qualitative costs and benefits of integration compared to stand-alone adaptation and mitigation policies. The analysis should be explicitly framed within the project's priorities and provide the foundation for evidence-based decision support tools. Besides, this dimension also considers the number of strategies which are delivered by DSS as key outcome to translate project's results into the real-world.

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2.4.9 Cross-sector and multi-scale

The 'Cross-sector and multi-scale' dimension integrates multiple disciplines, backgrounds and experiences in the co-development of a project, and describes the innovative combination of scales in the selection of DISTENDER case studies. As climate issues are complex and overcome geographical and sectoral boundaries, no one industrial sector can address them in their entirety. Likewise, climate change affects all levels of industry, the economy, and society. In line with this, research suggests that climate strategies are most effective when they are part of a diversified, but integrated portfolio with a large variety of sectoral measures, sector-specific criteria, and industry branches involved (Barker et al. 2007; Dhar and Khirfan 2017).

The two central concepts employed to achieve such cross-sectoral integration are transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary. The latter integrates experts from different disciplines whereas the former proliferates across disciplines and transcends the boundaries of experts' knowledge by empowering the civil society, associations and other external actors (Choi and Pak 2006). In DISTENDER, both the concepts are addressed by analysing their level of applicability. Besides, synergies between adaptation and mitigation strategies require the employment of a range of background input from various sectors in order to provide a complete picture of benefits and barriers deriving from climate strategies. Tools employed, such as risk assessment and global climate models, intersect different scales and assess the effectiveness within the downscaling chain. This dimension strongly influences all other impact dimensions. For example, transdisciplinarity strengthens collaboration and participation in cross-sectoral working groups. Likewise, interdisciplinarity is likely to improve interactions between policy and science, while promoting transparency, inclusivity and accessibility of results at multiple scales. Furthermore, in the finalized Decision Support System (DSS), the cross-sectoral and multi-scale dimension will be a crucial feature: Scalability on the one hand, and adaptability to a variety of sectoral contexts, on the other. Again, the underlying assumption is that climate change is and should be considered as a cross-cutting issue, affecting all levels of society and the economy. An analysis of this dimension brings also a better understanding of inconsistencies and overlaps between adaptation and mitigation strategies when it comes to their implementation within specific sectors. DISTENDER attempts to overcome such inconsistencies by identifying those conflicts and removing them in interplay between the strategies of different sectors.

2.4.10 Negative impacts

In recent years, climate change has become a fervently discussed issue; however, there is little consensus about the cumulative negative impacts on other areas of environmental politics and other policy fields which the increased focus on climate leads to (Agrawala et al. 2010). Negative impacts might cover a very broad range of issues from economic, social to environmental aspects. The identification of such negative impacts is likely to boost targeted-oriented actions and strengthen effective policies.

The evaluation of negative effects helps identifying criticalities and working on them, in order to strengthen project's effectiveness and work coordination. Contrary to all the other dimensions, there were only few direct 'outcomes' identified in this dimension. The dimension is understood as thematically overarching and conceptually separated from the other dimen-

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sions. The precise nature of the ‘measuring’ or ‘quantification’ of negative impacts is deliberately left open at this stage, but the dimension needs to be included in the framework, to prevent a one-sided evaluation of WP and project performance. Outcomes selected at this stage include insufficient levels of participation and engagement. DISTENDER will also pay attention to underrepresentation, for example among the relation men-women, and a potential lack sense of ownership that might affect the process of co-creation. As for impacts, potential conflicts between EU and local level are evaluated since they might lead to inefficient policymaking strategies. It might also happen that only a few stakeholders or sectors benefit from measures implemented and this condition is potentially harmful for social justice and inclusivity.

2.5 Conclusion: DISTENDER theory of change

To summarise, then, the theory of change for DISTENDER is constructed around a basic impact pathway consisting of outputs, outcomes, and impacts. To adapt the impact pathway to the specifics of the DISTENDER project, the monitoring team works backwards from the strategic objectives of the project and derives ten impact dimensions from them. In a later step, the concrete impacts are defined along the dimensions (3.2). To theoretically grasp the pathway toward the achievement of these impacts, two further elements are singled out from the project design: Assumptions about the direct changes (‘outcomes’) which the project is most likely to generate within its target groups, on the one hand, and the groups or products which the project’s success hinges on most critically, on the other. By making assumptions about reach, capacity, and behaviour in the context of the researchers, the case studies, and the Decision Support System which stands between them, the project monitoring team in a later step (3.1) creates a list of concrete outcomes which work toward the achievement of the impacts along the dimensions.

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Figure 2 The DISTENDER theory of change

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3 DISTENDER KPI framework

After the DISTENDER theory of change has been drawn up, this following chapter specifies the methodological basis for the data collection and quantification throughout the project. First, a distinction is made between different types of indicators; the monitoring team has developed so-called Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to fill the theoretical impact framework from the first chapter of this report with quantifiable data and assess the extent to which DISTENDER is on track to achieving optimal impact. Then, the characteristics defined for each individual indicator are elaborated on in detail, as well as the methodology for assessing the project's impact. The chapter closes with a few remarks on the envisioned communication strategy for utilizing the KPIs in the official project communication in collaboration with WP11 – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation.

3.1 Key Performance Indicators

3.1.1 Types of indicators

For climate change research and policy in particular, different types of indicators may be utilized for varying purposes; thus, the following section makes a necessary distinction of WP 10 Key Performance Indicators from other types of indicators also utilized in DISTENDER. These types of indicators are:

a) **Purely quantitative indicators for monitoring the progress of adaptation or mitigation measures.** This type of indicator is often used in local-level (smart city) projects (e.g., [SmartEnCity](#), see Annex I for more examples of projects and pertaining indicators) and serves to track progress of crucial concrete measures which are implemented in the respective city and contribute to the final goals in terms of sustainability, 'smartness', or resilience. Common indicators are, for example, 'number of EV charging points installed', 'number of trees planted', or 'share of total sealed public space unsealed'. These quantitative indicators require the maintenance of extensive databases and their continuous and meticulous updating. The indicators measure categories such as temporal or spatial extent of measures, monetary value, or the rate of change in percentages – this form of implementation monitoring is outside the scope of the DISTENDER project monitoring. As outlined above (1.2.1), some of this case study-specific work may be done in the context of T9.3, and collaboration between WP9 and WP10 on this is possible in the future.

b) **Purely quantitative process indicators for measuring project outputs** in accordance with the project management plan. Often, such indicators are simple numerical values. Data to quantify the indicators is collected on the number of statements released, paragraphs written, reports published. Outputs of project activities are counted for the purpose of project management and reporting. Some such KPIs are defined in the DISTENDER project proposal but will not be primarily employed by the monitoring team. Rather, they will be part of T1.1, T1.2, T1.3, and also utilized within the context of the communication and exploitation work (T11.1). The data required for these indicators is usually collected simultaneously to the work on the tasks and activities which are being monitored.

c) **Qualitative-quantitative indicators for measuring the impact of climate change.**

These indicators, which are crucial for climate change projections and impact assessments contain an element of both quantitative and qualitative data. The indicators can describe the scale as well as the depth of the impacts of climatic change. Parameters commonly employed in climate risk assessments are changes in heat, groundwater levels, or precipitation (see, e.g., Kahlenborn et al. 2021). While the selection of indicators to describe the impact of climate change within specific regions will differ according to geographical and climatic conditions, the entirety of indicators used is unchanging across contexts. The indicators themselves are not adapted to specific application contexts, but merely selected on the basis of the task and challenges at hand. Within DISTENDER, WP5 – Climate Risk and Impact Assessment is responsible for developing appropriate indicator sets for each case study and feed data into these sets in order to project climate risks and impacts within the pilots over the next thirty years. Indirectly, climate impact indicators can also be employed to measure the effectiveness of adaptation and resilience measures, e.g., when temperature changes over time are measured for an urban area subjected to greening and building measures, or when groundwater levels change in the aftermath of sponge city measures.

d) **Qualitative-quantitative indicators for measuring project outcomes.** This type of indicator is used to describe harder to measure changes like ‘motivation’, ‘satisfaction’, ‘sense of ownership’, or ‘increase in knowledge’. The indicators are qualitative-quantitative in the sense that they combine quantifiable data, such as aggregated Likert-scale responses with qualitative answers and assessments that add explanatory force to the results of the indicator data collection. These kinds of indicators are the focus of the DISTENDER project monitoring team (WP 10), and they have been successfully employed in the context of other EU-projects (e.g., [Life Sec Adapt](#)). The indicators developed for DISTENDER should be understood as a mix of process and outcome indicators (cf. Clarke 2021: 19): They measure the change in the outcomes of the project work throughout the project duration, so that the process itself may be modified if necessary. The indicators themselves are also open for modification in the future and are at points formulated in a deliberately open fashion.

3.1.2 Key Performance Indicators

The indicators picked for monitoring DISTENDER are labelled Key Performance Indicators, or, short, KPIs. The concept originally stems from the context of business management and performance evaluation (Parmenter 2020). In recent years, however, KPIs have gained prevalence in the context of measuring the longer-term impacts of smart city solution projects, of climate change measures, and vulnerability (Angelakoglu et al. 2019; Krisan 2022), as well as project monitoring and policy evaluation more generally (e.g., McCarthy et al. 2012).

KPIs offer a “type of language” to describe the effects and impacts of interventions and businesses (Warren 2011: 5). Particularly when it comes to measuring change over time, KPIs are viewed as a useful mechanism (cf. Clarke 2021: 3). In DISTENDER, the KPIs are indicators to monitor the project’s performance in terms of impacts. The KPIs themselves, however, do not measure the impacts directly, but are developed to measure the project outcomes and assess the extent to which these outcomes will lead to maximal impact in the specified dimensions.

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3.1.3 Procedure for DISTENDER KPI framework design

This section recapitulates the methodological approach taken in drawing up the present framework of Key Performance Indicators for the DISTENDER project. The work steps followed are common practice for indicator collection processes in similar climate change projects, particularly projects involving a large number of workstreams and stakeholders (Cf. Greiving et al. 2015: 309; Feldmeyer et al. 2019).

The work on the framework began with a review of other European and national-level projects in the context of adaptation, mitigation, climate change policy, smart city development, and energy transformation. A total of 36 EU projects was consulted. An overview of the projects scanned is found in Annex I. Next, a literature review of peer-reviewed work on impact monitoring and project evaluation was conducted, in order to set up a monitoring approach and an impact pathway for the project (Cf. 1.1-1.3). This theoretical frame was applied to the initial project design, and, on the basis of the project objectives, ten impact dimensions were developed (cf. 1.4). These dimensions were filled in with concrete Key Performance Indicator suggestions for each individual work package – in total, 8 indicator draft lists were created (one single list for WP2 – Stakeholder Engagement & Co-creation and WP9 – Case studies, and no lists for WP1 – Project Management, WP10 – Project Monitoring, and WP12 – Ethics). As described above (1.4), the impacts and outcomes are not necessarily work-package-specific, as the project's individual parts interlink very closely. The approach to create - at a first step - an individual list for each work package was chosen for pragmatic reasons: In order to enable the monitoring team to discuss the indicator suggestions in small focus groups, the indicator lists were split according to the work packages.

Following this groundwork, the lists, including a cover letter explaining the basic concepts of outcome and impact, as well as the purpose of the monitoring work, were sent out to the respective work package leaders and work package main contributors to set dates for individual work package meetings. Next, 11 meetings with a total of 30 participants from within the project consortium were held to discuss and co-develop the DISTENDER KPIs. In the course of these discussions, the work packages' participants were asked to share their own understanding of their individual contributions to the project work and their potential longer-term impacts. They also made suggestions regarding the precise formulation of indicators and their interplay with one another.

In the follow-up of these meetings, the monitoring team created a single KPI list from the 8 work-package-specific lists and the overarching long-term impacts were linked with their pertinent outcomes (cf. the lists in chapter 3). The indicator quantification and impact assessment methodology were refined further, and draft questionnaires were developed. All previous work results were collected in the present report and the finalised indicator list was returned to the work package leaders of the project for revision and additional comments. This was done to ensure that the impact monitoring is a co-production of the monitoring team and those consortium members whose impacts will be monitored throughout the duration of DISTENDER.

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3.2 KPI characteristics

The KPIs developed for measuring the DISTENDER outcomes are specified and distinguished by eight characteristics: Their numerical identifier, their name, a detailed description, the WP co-owning the KPI (if applicable), the unit in which they are measured, the method by which they are measured, as well as the frequency of measurement and their primary addressee. This section discusses all eight categories in turn – the section following this one elaborates on the methodology for the data collection and the final assessment of impacts during and at the end of the project. The impact indicators are only classified by their identifier, their name, a detailed description, as well as by the outcomes contributing to their achievement (see 2.3.4).

3.2.1 Identifier / number

The outcome KPIs (see 3.1) are numbered consecutively from O.1 to O.115. The individual numbers are simply used for identification and differentiation of indicators and have no meaning beyond this. The impacts are numbered consecutively, as well, from I.44. In linking impacts and outcomes, some outcomes need further specification according to the context within which they will be measured. As an example, an indicator like O.3 ('Workshop quality') will not be measured once, but across workshops conducted for different purposes. Thus, the indicator may be split across impacts as O.3.a (relating to 'socioeconomic scenario design workshops'), O.3.b (relating to 'climate scenario design workshops'), O.3.c (relating to 'climate impact assessment workshops'), etc. This will also provide the monitoring team with some flexibility regarding the attribution of data toward each individual impact later in the monitoring process.

3.2.2 Name and description

A short, easy-to-grasp, name and a more in-depth qualitative description for each indicator are given in the first two columns of both indicator tables (3.1 and 3.2). The in-depth description elaborates on the name tag and outlines the interpretive value and usability of the individual indicators.

3.2.3 Co-owner

Co-owners of the indicators developed are always other work packages of DISTENDER. While all KPIs are first and foremost 'owned', i.e., measured, quantified, and evaluated by WP10, for some indicators the support of other experts from the project is desirable. The primary contact person for the co-owners will, naturally, be the work package leader, but the whole work package with all its contributors is included by the category. Co-ownership means that the respective work packages will be co-responsible for measuring, quantifying and evaluating each individual KPI. Most indicators are owned by WP10. For some indicators, there may be co-owners. Specifically, WP2, WP9, and WP11 support the collection of indicators through their own areas of activity, respectively: Stakeholder engagement, case study engagement, and communication/dissemination.

3.2.4 Unit

The **unit** refers to the specific parameter by which the indicator is described. The category unit is strongly interlinked with the chosen *method* of indicator quantification. In some cases,

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the unit is numerical and quantitative (e.g., a score, percentage, scale, or number of people), in others it is qualitative (e.g., open responses). In choosing the appropriate unit for each indicator, the specific phenomenon being assessed by the indicator, the methods most suitable, as well as the data most likely available were considered.

3.2.5 Method

This category is related to the **method** applied in measuring individual indicators: Surveys, interviews, and direct observation are chief among the monitoring methods adopted in DISTENDER. In most cases, a 5-point Likert scale will be applied for evaluating questionnaires and thematic analyses through interviews and workshops. For further elaboration on the methodology of indicator quantification and impact calculation, see the following section 2.3.

3.2.6 Frequency of measurement

The **measurement interval** provides the temporal scale for measuring each specific indicator. It is based on the biyearly monitoring cycles fixed in the proposal for the project and thus often indicated with the value 'Biannually'. An update of the evaluation indicators should take place at least every six months and, accordingly, a first monitoring report will be delivered 6 months after the submission of the framework (M12, May 2023). The actual measuring for this first report should take place about 3 months after D10.1 has been submitted (M9, February 2023). This will primarily serve the establishment of baselines for the indicators.

For the second report (due in M36, May 2025), further measuring will take place in M15 (August 2023), M21 (February 2024), M27 (August 2024), and M33 (February 2025). For the final impact assessment (M42, December 2025), a final round of indicator quantification is set to take place in M39 (August 2025).

Since only two progress reports with a comprehensive update of all indicators will be published during the project duration (D10.2 and D10.3), but the reporting on the indicators toward the project team is supposed to take place more often, provisions have been taken for less comprehensive and more targeted update sessions and workshops (see 2.4 on the internal communication strategy).

3.2.7 Addressee

Addressees are those stakeholders of DISTENDER or other groups which will be addressed during the measuring of the indicator. The addressees are the sources of the data; they either provide already-existing data directly, or they are interviewed or surveyed in order to produce the data. The addressees of individual indicators should be defined clearly *before* the measuring phase begins, because in many cases the surveys and interview questionnaires will need to be adapted, depending on who is being addressed. This early definition was done in cooperation with the stakeholder engagement and co-creation work packages and will be updated accordingly. For now, the addressee category draws on a draft version of D2.1 (coming out of T2.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping) which is still being prepared at the time of publication of this report, as well as the multiple exchanges which took place with WP2 – Stakeholder Engagement & Co-creation and WP9 – Case studies during the preparation of the present deliverable.

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At this early stage of the project work, not all specific stakeholders of the project have been identified and classified. The addressees are broadly separated into the researchers of the project, the case studies, and external stakeholders. These groups are further specified, when KPIs require specific thematic expertise or sectoral experience. Potential KPI-addressees thus are:

- **Stakeholders.** This refers to all direct stakeholders of the DISTENDER project, including the researchers from all work packages, the funding agency, and all stakeholders involved from the side of the core and follower case studies. The precise definition of the category will depend on the results of T2.1.
- **Case studies.** This specifies the stakeholder group to be addressed and refers to the direct representatives from the core case studies. In some instances, these representatives might be asked to provide contact points to further relevant individuals or institutions from their case study which might help with the quantification of a specific indicator. Mostly, this will refer to the policymakers from the respective case studies primarily; if policymakers are to be addressed exclusively, this is noted in the table.
- **Follower case studies.** This category refers exclusively to the direct representatives from the follower case studies. Again, if policymakers are to be addressed exclusively, this is noted in the table.
- **External stakeholders.** This broader category, which refers to stakeholders from the context of the case studies, as well as stakeholders from elsewhere identified by WP2 (*if such stakeholders will be identified*), may include a wide variety of actors. In some cases, the category is already subdivided into more specific descriptions (such as ‘financial service providers’ or ‘SMEs’), in other cases, a more specific description will need to be decided on once the measuring phase has begun.
- **Researchers.** This category refers to *all* researchers from *all* work packages of DISTENDER. In practice, not all members of the ECAS system will be surveyed, but a broad and representative group of researchers to be surveyed should be chosen from across the work packages.
- **WP1; WP2; WP3; ...** The **Work packages** may also be addressed individually, especially when the indicator relates to the outcomes produced by the respective work package’s direct output.

3.3 Methodology for indicator data collection and quantification

The DISTENDER technical KPI framework mainly relies on a mix of predesigned surveys and semi-structured interviews throughout the project for the collection of data for project monitoring. Additionally, the members of the monitoring team will act as observers in workshops, focus groups, and other work package meetings to monitor general project progress. The main methods envisioned to be utilized throughout are elaborated on in the following. Then, the crucial question of how to assess the level of achievement of the impacts from the outcome KPIs is tackled.

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3.3.1 Surveys

Surveys, in the form of online and in-person questionnaires, are one of the data collection methods used in DISTENDER. First, a pre-test is carried out: a specified group of stakeholders is asked to fill in the form and comment on the questions. Then, online questionnaires are shared through e.g. GoogleForm or LimeSurvey. A certain number of multiple, single-choice and open questions constitute the questionnaire. One of the main characteristics of DISTENDER's survey is its quantitative-qualitative nature: Information is collected in the form of numerical scores and qualitative answers in order to cross-verify specific impact dimensions. For example, the number of events in which a participant participated is connected with a question regarding his/her level of satisfaction and involvement, as well as formulated comments, like suggestions for future similar events. The level of participation, satisfaction, etc. will be elaborated through a 5-Point Likert Scale (e.g. from 1=Not at all/ Not important/ Strongly Disagree to 5=Very much/ Very important/ Strongly Agree). The values of Likert Scales will be further translated into numerical information by using Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics²⁷ Software. The software will compute the average mean of the 5-Point Likert Scale and make possible cross-sectoral analysis of different variables. For example, participants' individual characteristics (e.g. gender, scientists-policy makers) are cross-tabulated with their responses regarding satisfaction, willingness, motivation, etc. These results will be visualized (e.g. bar charts) via Excel and SPSS. Keywords will instead be extracted from open questions and a thematic analysis will follow in order to understand the relevance of certain topics.

3.3.2 Interviews

Interviews will be semi-structured. This means that questions will be partly set in advance and partly free, meaning that they develop naturally from the individual conversations. During the project, interviews are carried out through both face-to-face and virtually. A core characteristic of the interviews in DISTENDER project monitoring is the make-up of the respondent groups. Indeed, a highly heterogeneous group of people will be involved as regards their position within the project (e.g. modellers, WPs leaders etc.), personal characteristics (a balanced number of women and men), and their role within the society (representative of civil society, associations etc.). The precise addressees for each individual outcome indicator are pre-specified (see above 2.2.7), but may be altered and adapted as the project evolves. Both addressees' opinions and professional knowledge will be included in the indicator quantification. For example, specific interviews with core case studies will aim at collecting their understanding on specific topics, but also at identifying whether new best practices for dealing with climate change have been developed among them, and whether they feel capable and willing of implementing these measures.

3.3.3 Observation

DISTENDER will also apply what is here termed 'observation' as one of its methodologies to assess the project's development. Observations will be carried out by WP10 itself (*direct observations*) or by WPs leaders (*indirect observations*) who then report to WP10 who in turn analyses and interprets the indirect observations. Workshops and roundtables will be the main grounds for observations. Furthermore, actions and results are evaluated at two

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different levels: a) individually and b) collectively. As for the former, each individual participant in a workshop will be observed. In other cases, a group of individuals will be considered as a whole to extract information about their role in the participatory processes. For example, 'observation' will be employed as the method for assessing the group's composition, their level of interaction with other participants, and potential new words and concepts entering their vocabulary and being employed in discourse.

3.3.4 Assessment of impacts

Impacts are measured and assessed starting from interlinked outcomes. These outcomes are located within the dimensions described in Chapter 1.4 and they are selected based on their salience and coherency with respect to each dimension. Indeed, each impact will be constituted by one or more outcome indicator(s), or KPIs. Outcomes (and their combination) will constitute the core elements to measure and evaluate project's impacts.

The DISTENDER monitoring team has created an initial list of 115 outcomes which are visualized in Table 5. They differ in their nature, method of applicability, and scale of measurement. For example, there are qualitative and quantitative outcomes which might be measured by using open questions or statistical methods. In order to be assessed, all of the outcomes need to be a) measurable; b) comparable; c) combinable with other outcomes to constitute a coherent impact. To this end, the DISTENDER monitoring team will apply the following steps:

1) Create a list of outcomes represented by Key Performance Indicators. A list of outcomes has been identified and interlinked with a corresponding impact list (cf. 2.1.3 for the indicator collection procedure). The selection of outcomes that constitute a single impact will be based on: 1) Their relevance within the impact's dimension; 2) their nature since it is preferred having a combination of quantitative and qualitative outcomes constituting the same impact; 3) their temporal scale of applicability since all the outcomes need to be roughly measured at the same time.

2) Measure each individual indicator throughout the project duration and render indicators comparable amongst each other by applying a 5-point scale. Each outcome then needs to be measured applying quantitative methods. Purely qualitative outcomes will be translated into numerical values. A 5-point scale will be employed for each outcome in order to make them comparable with other outcomes. Satisfaction will be measured through a 5-point Likert Scale, number of reports will be converted in a 5-level scale, % of cities that applied a specific tool will be converted in 5-point numerical values. This will be the prerequisite for Step 4.

3) Apply weights for each indicator by combining different scales. Based on the number of outcomes constituting an impact, DISTENDER will weight each outcome equally. Therefore, two outcomes constituting an impact will be weight 50% each, while a single outcome forming an impact will be valued as 100%. The value in percentage will be translated into numerical value ranging from 0 to 1. 50% will be translated into 0.5 and 100% into 1.

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4) Calculate the impacts by combining the weighted outcomes. Values obtained in Step 2 and 3 will be used to measure each impact, which will have a value ranging from 0-1. This will be obtained by multiplying the sum of points achieved in Step 2) divided for 5 -which represents the 5-point scale - by the weight value from Step 3).

5) Evaluate all impacts and their level of achievement qualitatively. The numerical value that come out will define each impact. It will lastly be qualitatively evaluated. This step will assess whether a certain impact has been achieved / is likely to be achieved fully, partially or not. This might be shown as a percentage. In this way, impact's effectiveness and success will emerge. It will also be compared with other impacts giving an overview of which impact has been mostly effectively achieved.

As an example, consider an Impact A ('Municipal network best practices') which 3 outcomes have been connected to: Outcome a (*Out.a*), Outcome b (*Out.b*) and Outcome c (*Out.c*). Outcome a reveals that 3 cities out of 5 plan to have stakeholders' roundtables, Outcome b shows that 80% of cities applied a certain innovative method, whereas Outcome c highlights that every stakeholder is satisfied about the innovative method applied. Thus, respectively, the values of the three outcomes in a 5-point Scale are: **Point 3 out of 5** (Outcome a), **Point 4 out of 5** (Outcome b), **Point 5 out of 5** (Outcome c). Subsequently, outcomes are weighted as described in Step 3. In this case, three outcomes constitute an impact. Each outcome will account for 1/3 to the overall impact. Numerically this means 0.33333 in a scale from 0-1. Given the values identified in the previous steps, the Impact A will be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Impact A} = \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{\text{Out.a} + \text{Out.b} + \text{Out.c}}{5}$$

N= Number of outcomes

Following the above example, the equation is:

$$\text{Impact A} = \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{3+4+5}{5} = \mathbf{0,8}$$

Concretely, this means that the Impact A, 'Municipal networking best practices' is evaluated at a level of 80%. This means that the project has seen a moderate level of participation among cities that exhaustively applied an innovative method strongly appreciated among stakeholders.

3.4 Dealing with Uncertainties at KPI level

One major aspect in setting up the monitoring system is the reliability of the information. The final results measured by KPIs should be clearly referring to the underlying question, be unequivocal and be replicable. Also, the KPIs should gauge to the maximum possible the eventual impact.

Uncertainties regarding the KPIs cannot be avoided, but they can be mitigated. The use of various methods to collect information (as demonstrated above) is one approach to reduce

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uncertainties. Also, various efforts to make sure that the number of project participants answering the questions and thus providing the necessary information for calculating the KPIs is as high as possible, is another approach which will dampen any outliers.

Intense discussions with the various WP partners on the formulation of the question themselves is important to make sure that the questions are understood by all in the same and correct way. The team has made several loops with the WP partners to discuss the respective questions with them. Also, keeping in mind not to use too complex phrases and to be really clear in the question increases the likelihood of obtaining the right answers. Allowing for the possibility to clarify any open issues directly with the WP 10 team supports project partners in providing their information.

By collecting additional qualitative contextual information apart from the information which directly goes into the calculation of the KPIs we make sure, that the KPIs are interpreted in the correct way and limitations in the application of the KPIs can be made clear.

3.5 Communication strategy

Communicating project progress, results, and impacts both internally and externally is a core function of Key Performance Indicators (see above 2.1). The communication of the Key Performance Indicator framework will be approached in close collaboration and exchange with WP11 – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. This section briefly outlines, first, the DISTENDER-internal communication process of the indicator results, and, secondly, the relationship and interaction between work packages 10 and 11 on communicating DISTENDER's impacts towards the outside.

Within DISTENDER, the results of the indicator quantification are intended to support the work of the remaining work packages and ensure that they achieve their goals in the best possible way. According to the design of WP10, the indicator data collection is supposed to be conducted (see above 2.2.6) and reported on every six months. While only two official progress reports are scheduled to be released during the project duration (D10.2 and D10.3), the KPI results will be more regularly reported on through the channel of official meetings between WP10 and the other work package leaders. These meetings will be convened at least every six months and more frequently should WP10 consider them necessary, e.g., due to pressing issues identified in project implementation. The entirety of the results will then be edited and interpreted in the two planned official progress reports (see above 2.2.6).

Externally, the main target groups for the communication of the KPIs will be the scientific community and actors contributing to policy making processes at national and European level. Beyond this, impacts of DISTENDER should also be communicated towards the broader population, at least within the context of the case studies, as this is likely to further increase these very impacts.

WP11 is responsible for this external communication via the DISTENDER website and various online channels. WP11 will also employ analogous tools for publicization, such as printed publications and flyers which will be distributed, for example, at in-person EU Horizon workshops. The precise approach taken to the communication and dissemination of the project results will be laid out in D11.1 and D11.2. Regarding the utilization of KPIs, WP11

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will self-directly develop and apply quantitative KPIs to measure the success of DISTENDER's engagement throughout. WP10 will collect the results of these KPIs to quantify DISTENDER impacts (see, e.g., I.32 below).

At the same time, however, the results collected by WP10 on the basis of the impact KPIs may provide additional information and value to be communicated to the relevant target groups. For this purpose, a strong link between WP10 and WP11 has been established and continuous exchange is planned. In addition to the official internal meetings with all work package leaders, regular meetings between WP10 and WP11 (*jour fixes*) will be scheduled at the beginning of M7 of the project. They will take place on a bimonthly basis and provide the opportunity for updating WP11 about recent developments and findings on DISTENDER's impacts. The meetings will also serve as a platform for WP11 to suggest specific questions or aspects of the project which the monitoring team should put more emphasis and focus on, in order to improve the contents, quality, and information value of the communication material of the project.

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4 Indicator lists

4.1 Outcomes

Table 5: DISTENDER outcomes

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
Co-creation	O.1	Understanding of co-creation	Degree of to which stakeholders understand co-creation elements (barriers, constraints, tools, ...)	WP2	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Interviews/ Survey	Case studies
	O.2	Continuity in stakeholder interaction	How many 'rounds of interaction' / regularity of engagement [per stakeholder] Frequency ('how often?') and duration ('how long?') of core stakeholder participation	WP2	[#]	Biannually	Observation	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.3	Workshop quality	Stakeholder satisfaction regarding workshops conducted	WP2 Case studies	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders WPs involved in workshops
	O.4	Willingness for adoption of method	Willingness to replicate method of co-creation in the context of other policy fields (e.g., urban planning)	WP2	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
Participation	O.5	New vulnerabilities identified	No. of (key) stakeholders which identify previously neglected vulnerabilities + subjective assessment of their relevance	WP5	[#] + Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.6	Stakeholder diversity and inclusion	Assessment of stakeholder composition [financial service providers; SMEs; institutional/private investors] [available capital] [public sector financial regulatory power] [gender balance] [...]	WP2	List + [%] of groups per context	Biannually	Observation	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.7	Stakeholder analysis applicability in processes	Extent to which stakeholder analysis is reflected in participatory processes (e.g., workshops)	WP2	Score	Biannually	Observation	WP2 WP3
	O.8	Stakeholder analysis applicability in results	Extent to which stakeholder analysis is reflected in results (e.g., socio-economic scenarios)	WP2	Score	Annually	Observation	WP2 WP3
	O.9	Sense of involvement in climate change challenges	Sense of involvement and perceived stake in climate change challenges	-	Likert scale 1-5 ⁵	Annually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.10	Ownership of project results	Sense of ownership of results of the project as a whole	-	Likert scale 1-5	Annually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

⁵ Baseline will be adopted from CS self-descriptions submitted to WP9 – Case studies.

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.11	Individual contribution	Sense of ownership of specific results of the workstream stakeholders are involved in	-	Likert scale 1-5 ⁶	Annually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.12	Financial service provider integration	Satisfaction of financial service providers regarding participatory development of business models [depends on previous rounds of interactions whether this kind of stakeholder is engaged]	WP7	Likert scale 1-5	Annually	Survey	External stakeholders (financial service providers)
	O.13	SME integration	Satisfaction of small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) stakeholders regarding participatory development of business models	WP7	Score + Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	External stakeholders (SMEs)
	O.14	Involvement of impacted non-financial actors	Level of involvement of non-finance DISTENDER stakeholders affected/impacted by financing schemes	WP7	Score + Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	External stakeholders (non-finance)
	O.15	Diversity of platforms	Diversity of engagement platforms: Alternative channels to reach difficult-to-reach demographics are tapped	WP11	List + Qualitative responses	Annually	Survey or interview	WP11
	O.16	Practical engagement	Extent to which concrete options and ideas for citizens to engage and/or participate are provided	WP11	Score + Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey or interview	WP11
	O.17	Successful outreach	Extent to which Communication, dissemination, and exploitation KPIs are achieved ⁷	WP11	[%]	Biannually	Observation	WP11

⁶ Baseline will be created from stakeholders' 'initial expectation' of their individual contribution.

⁷ For the quantification of WP11-related indicators, WP10 will work together with WP11 and take recourse to the WP11-specific KPIs listed in the DISTENDER Grant Agreement.

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
Network	O.18	Network for sharing climate change experience	Extent to which risk assessments have been supportive in creating stakeholder networks	WP5	[%] of networks integrating vulnerability assessment	Biannually	Survey	Stakeholders
	O.19	Exchange on strategies	Connections made between stakeholders on exchanging experiences and best practices from other pilot studies	WP6	Score + Qualitative response	Annually	Survey	Case studies
	O.20	Potential DSS networks	No. and extent of (potential) networks formed around the DSS	WP8 WP11	[#] / map Data on end users	Near project end	Survey and interviews	Case studies Follower case studies ⁸
	O.21	DSS scientific networks	Extent to which researchers regard the DSS as having the potential for long-term interdisciplinary cooperation	WP8	Score	Biannually	Survey	Researchers from all WPs
	O.22	Continuity of networks	Willingness of network members to keep up structures after project end	–	Score	Annually	Survey	Network members (e.g., in the context of conferences)
Science-policy and	O.23	Guideline comprehensibility	Extent to which modelling results and information are communicated to decisionmakers clearly, concretely, concisely, and coherently	–	Score + Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)

⁸ Will evaluate the progress of the networking

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
science-science interaction	O.24	Impact assessment comprehensibility	Extent to which policymakers feel capable of 'reading' climate risk and impact assessments (WP5 results)	WP5	Likert scale 1-5 + Qualitative responses	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.25	Awareness of uncertainties	Extent to which uncertainties are considered in WP work: Methodological improvement, e.g., through better qualification of potential uncertainties	WP3 WP6	Score + Qualitative responses Statistics (e.g., [#] of projections, consensus or spread metrics)	Annually	Survey	WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7
	O.26	Usefulness and integration potential of results for policy-making	Extent to which stakeholders see potential integration of WP results into existing policies	–	Score + Qualitative response	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.27	Awareness of scientific methods	Awareness in scientific projects (e.g., using data, modelling processes, etc.)	–	List with individual methods + [Y/N]	Baseline at project start Change at project end	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.28	Understanding of scientific methods	Improved understanding of scientific methods in research projects (e.g., data, processes, and decision-making)	–	List with individual methods + Likert	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.29	Technical understanding of governance	Improved understanding of stakeholder requirements for scientific input, e.g., at different government levels	WP2 WP9	List with individual requirements + Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Researchers
	O.30	Understanding of stakeholder requirements	Policymakers' impression of whether scientists have grasped case study problems adequately	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies
	O.31	Enhanced compliance	Extent to which scientific solutions developed from risk assessments support existing policies and strategies, e.g., EU Green Deal	–	Likert scale 1-5	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers) WP6
	O.32	Pertinence of climate model inputs	Lessons learned regarding pertinent input data to climate models run	–	Score + Qualitative response	Biannually	Survey	WP4
	O.33	Relevance of scenarios developed	Extent to which developed scenarios cover stakeholders' existing climate change challenges	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders WP3 WP4
	O.34	Learning capacity regarding methodologies	Extent to which follower case studies are able to learn from downscaling techniques and the co-design of climate indicators	WP4 WP5	Score + Qualitative response	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (including modellers)

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
								External stakeholders (including modellers)
	O.35	Successful integration of models and impact assessments	Extent to which impact modellers are able to work with climate model outputs	WP4 WP5	Likert + Qualitative response	After each completion of a model run	Survey	WP5
	O.36	Understanding of DISTENDER project as a whole	Scientists' impression of whether policymakers have grasped DISTENDER project goals	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP6
	O.37	Understanding of existing policy framework	Extent to which more comprehensive overview of the state of policy in respective case study is achieved, as well as conflicts and interactions	WP6	Score	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers) Researchers
	O.38	Understanding of existing conflicts and interactions	Improved understanding of conflicts and interactions between existing strategies	WP6	Score	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers) Researchers
	O.39	Adoption of financial models	Results of WP7 are relevant for political stakeholders	WP7	[#] or list of tools + Score	Biannually	Observation Survey	Case studies
	O.40	Adoption of cost-benefit evaluation tools for policy-making	Governance or government institutions see added value in employing cost-benefit evaluation tools (such as benefit transfer techniques) in their day-to-day work	WP7	List of participating institutions + Score	Biannually	Observation Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.41	Relevance of project results for EU decisionmakers	Results of WP7 are relevant for design of EU funding schemes	WP7	Score	End of project	Survey Desk re-search	WP7 EU funding schemes
	O.42	Access of policymakers and other stakeholders to science	Extent to which scientific output is delivered and communicated in accessible language ('semantics') and comprehensible reasoning ('logic')	-	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.43	Adequate model of reality	Extent to which DSS is considered to adequately and realistically represent the complex environments which policymakers must navigate	WP8	Score + Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.44	Researchers satisfaction regarding presentation of results in DSS	Extent to which researchers regard their outputs to be translated adequately into the DSS	WP8	Score	Biannually	Survey	Researchers
Awareness / understanding	O.45	Innovative science communication	New concepts / communication tools developed	WP11	[#]	Biannually	Observation	WP3 WP4
	O.46	Key concept formulation and adoption	Formulation and proper adoption of key concepts which emerge from the project	WP9	[#] of mentions per keyword in survey Adequacy scale	End of project	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.47	Awareness of concepts of adaptation and mitigation	Understanding of the definition and distinction of climate adaptation and climate mitigation (cf. T9.1)	WP9	[#] of examples	Beginning and end of project	Survey	Case studies

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
					and accuracy [Y/N]			External stakeholders
	O.48	Sectoral risk awareness	Survey about understanding of climate risks in climate-sensitive sectors (cf. T4.1)	WP4 WP5	Score	Annually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.49	Understanding of concept of vulnerability	Extent to which DISTENDER refines and broadens external stakeholders' understanding of climate change impacts and risk (socioeconomic + climate) – [e.g., interrelation of exposure, vulnerability, coping capacity]	–	Test score	Annually	Testing	Stakeholders
	O.50	Understanding of uncertainties of model outputs	Extent to which external stakeholders understand potential uncertainties of model outputs (and their characteristics, e.g., internal/external uncertainties)	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.51	Understanding of uncertainties of modeling process	Confidence regarding uncertainties considered in modelling; linking models; parameters	–	Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	WP3 WP4 WP5
	O.52	Comprehensibility of results	Understanding of the results of climate change risk assessment	WP5	Score (based on concrete examples)	Annually	Survey	Stakeholders
	O.53	Conceptual depth	Understanding of the concepts 'synergy' and 'trade-off' in the context of climate adaptation and climate mitigation	WP6	Score	Annually	Survey	Stakeholders

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.54	Awareness of potentially conflicting nature of adaptation and mitigation interaction	New climate change strategies exclude or acknowledge the possibility of adverse effects of adaptation or mitigation measures on mitigation or adaptation efforts, respectively	WP6	[#] and [%]	Annually	Observation	Case studies
	O.55	Awareness of potentially synergistic nature of adaptation and mitigation interaction	New climate change strategies exclude or acknowledge the possibility of positive effects of adaptation or mitigation measures on mitigation or adaptation efforts, respectively	WP6	[#] and [%]	Annually	Observation	Case studies
	O.56	Bundling of individual measures into strategies	Individual mitigation or adaptation measures are recognised as part of mitigation or adaptation strategy and bundled into a strategy	WP6	[#] measures/ stakeholders [#] strategies first labelled as such	Once at start of WP6 (M12)	Survey	Case studies
	O.57	Knowledge about context-specific financing regulations	Extent to which previous knowledge about climate change financing (e.g., EU taxonomy) is furthered through DISTENDER	WP7	Score	Annually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.58	Visualisation of climate change issues	Accurate and useful visualisation of complex climate change issues	WP8 WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey	Researchers Case studies
	O.59	Interlinking of climate change issues	Extent to which the complex interconnectedness of climate change issues is represented accurately through the DSS	WP8 WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey	Researchers Case studies

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
Details	O.60	Awareness about adaptation and mitigation integration	Extent to which awareness about adaptation and mitigation integration changes with the interested public during project duration	WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey ⁹	Interested public
	O.61	Awareness about participatory models for climate change action	Extent to which awareness about participatory models for climate change action changes with citizens during project duration	WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey ¹⁰	Citizens
	O.62	Awareness about SSPs/RCPs	Extent to which awareness about SSPs/RCPs changes with policymakers during project duration	WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey ¹¹	Policymakers
	O.63	Awareness about downscaling methods	Extent to which awareness about downscaling methods changes with scientists during project duration	WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey ¹²	Scientists
	O.64	Engagement of third-party researchers	Extent to which third parties are reached through other EU research projects and networks which they belong to	–	[%] + List	Annually	Survey	WP11
Implementation	O.65	Accessibility of project results	Extent to which follower case studies can access and understand results of projects	WP9	Score	Annually	Survey	Follower case studies
	O.66	Capacity to use and correctly interpret model outputs	Extent to which policymakers feel capable of interpreting and utilizing model outputs in policy design	–	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)

⁹ Numeric information provided by WP11.

¹⁰ Numeric information provided by WP11.

¹¹ Numeric information provided by WP11.

¹² Numeric information provided by WP11.

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.67	Availability and usability of local-level data	Extent to which modellers are able to make use of local-level climate/socio-economic data	WP3 WP4	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP4 WP5
	O.68	Creation of multi-dimensional climate simulations	No. of individual local/regional climate simulations obtained by combination (multi-projection ensemble) of downscaled Earth System Models under different socioeconomic scenarios	WP4	[#]	Annually	Observation	WP4
	O.69	Extensibility of downscaling techniques	No. of downscaled techniques tested and finally used % to which models have been scaled down under which % of socioeconomic scenarios	WP4	[#] or [%]	Biannually	Observation	WP4
	O.70	Downscaling area	Smallest area covered by model after downscaling and spatial resolution	WP4	[%] and m ²	Biannually	Observation	WP4
	O.71	Downscaling costs	Costs of the downscaling processes [computing + energy + staff + ...]	WP4	Score or, if numerical values not possible, qualitative response	Annually	Survey	WP4
	O.72	Pertinent indicators	Extent to which challenges and vulnerabilities identified by stakeholders are addressed by the indicators developed	WP5	Likert scale 1-5 + Qualitative response	Biannually	Survey	Case studies
	O.73	Indicator adoption	No. of indicators (impact, or vulnerability, or coping capacity, ...) adopted on case-study level	WP5	[#] or [%]	Biannually	Observation	Case studies

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
					Ranking per case study			
	O.74	Indicator application	Confidence of policymakers that policies can be adapted on the basis of climate change indicator data	WP5	Likert scale 1-5	Annually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.75	Multi-scale applicability of indicators	Extent to which researchers feel confident that indicators are applicable across scales	WP5	Likert scale 1-5 or qualitative response	Biannually	Survey	WP5
	O.76	Policy downscaling	No. of aspects of EU strategies integrated into local strategies ['aspects': policy measures, challenges addressed, fields of action]	WP6	[#] and list	Biannually	Observation	WP6
	O.77	Streamlining national-local strategy interaction	No. of (legislative and regulatory) inconsistencies (e.g., different levels of ambition; conflicts) identified in interplay between national and local level policies	WP6	[#]	Biannually	Observation	WP6
	O.78	Readiness for new climate adaptation and climate mitigation tools	Motivation or willingness to install new processes, techniques, or institutional provisions on consistent climate adaptation and mitigation policy	WP6	[Y/N] + [#] across case studies	End of project	Observation	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.79	Integration of government departments	Extent to which previously segregated government departments (e.g., responsible for adaptation or mitigation, respectively) establish connections due to DISTENDER	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.80	Reproducible methods for robust strategy design	Extent to which follower case studies are able to design their own robust strategies	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Follower case studies
	O.81	Reproducible strategies	Extent to which follower case studies are able to replicate strategies or individual measures applied in pilot cases	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Follower case studies
	O.82	Financial innovation	Willingness to adopt innovative schemes for financing and participatory business models	WP7	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.83	Usefulness of DSS for strategy design	Willingness to use DSS for strategy design beyond project duration	WP8	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.84	Dissemination of DSS	Feedback from third parties on interest in/willingness to use DSS within their own specific contexts	WP11	Score	Biannually	Survey/ observation	WP11
Cost-efficiency	O.85	Coherency of cost-benefit analyses across sectors	Are the results of the cost-benefit analysis accurate?	External evaluators	–	End of project	External evaluation	Third party expert(s) from sectors
	O.86	Individual applicability of cost-efficiency	Extent to which stakeholders can derive cost-efficiency of individual particular measures from WP7 results	WP7	Score	From modelling round 3 onward	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.87	Adaptability of DSS outcomes to users' financial capacities	DSS end-users consider the DSS recommendations to be financially applicable or feasible	–	Score ¹³	Final year of project	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)

¹³ Ranked according to scales: SME; municipal public spending; etc.

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.88	Increased funding potential	Increased willingness of stakeholders to redirect funding to climate change measures on basis of DSS outcomes	WP7 WP8	Score / [€] from base-line	Final year of project	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.89	Adequate balance between costs and benefits	DSS end-users consider DSS cost-efficiency analyses to be realistic, e.g.: Are <i>benefits</i> reflected appropriately in relation to costs and calculated in an appropriate manner?	WP8	Score, differentiated by stakeholder	Final year of project	Survey	Stakeholders
	O.90	Cost-efficient replicability	Extent to which DSS can be used (cheaply) by third parties	WP8 WP11	Qualitative responses	Final year of project	Survey	Third parties WP8
Integration of CA and CM	O.91	Differentiated consideration/balance of adaptation and mitigation in socioeconomic scenarios	Specific individual elements within socioeconomic scenarios relating to adaptation and mitigation, respectively	WP3	Score	Biannually	Survey	...
	O.92	Increased mitigative action	Willingness to develop mitigation measures at case-study scale	WP9 WP2	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Policymakers
	O.93	Increased adaptive action	Willingness to develop adaptation measures at case-study scale	WP9 WP2	Likert scale 1-5	Biannually	Survey	Policymakers
	O.94	Awareness of adaptation/mitigation synergies	Understanding of (dis)advantages of integrating adaptation and mitigation	WP9	[#] of examples and accuracy [Y/N]	Beginning and end of project	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.95	Sensitivity of the models to the adaptation/mitigation input data	Extent to which model output quality differs depending on type of input data	–	Likert scale 1-5 + Qualitative response	Annually	Survey	WP4
	O.96	Appropriateness of indicators for integration adaptation and mitigation	Extent to which WP5 indicators were useful for developing integrated adaptation or mitigation actions	WP5	[#]	Biannually	Survey	Case studies WP6
	O.97	Sensitivity of impact models	Climate change impact analysis is capable of assessing vulnerability with and without implementation of adaptation measures	WP5	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP5
	O.98	Actual implementation of integrated measures	No. of strategies evaluated and identified as robust by WP6 that are implemented after evaluation, standard of quality of these strategies	–	[%] + Score	Near end of the project	Survey	Case studies (policymakers)
	O.99	Policy innovation	Innovative (meaning ‘never implemented before within respective case-study context’) individual policy measure tackling both climate adaptation and mitigation implemented or added to strategies	–	[#] + List	Near end of the project	Survey	Case studies (policymakers) WP6
	O.100	Financial integration	Assessment of results of T7.2 and T7.3 regarding the successful integration of adaptation and mitigation, i.e.: How well is the method suited to make ‘integrated’ financial assessments?	–	Score	Annually	Survey	WP7
	O.101	Real-world implementation	No. of strategies delivered by DSS that are implemented after evaluation	WP8	[%] + Score	End of the project	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

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Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
Cross-sector / multi-scale	O.102	Multiscale and multidimensional socioeconomic scenarios	Socioeconomic scenarios are applicable/adaptable across different scales and sectors	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP3
	O.103	Project interdisciplinarity	Level of interdisciplinarity: No. and type of disciplines and research domains covered by stakeholders involved (demographic variables)	–	[#]	During stakeholder mapping and throughout project	Observation	WP2 WP9
	O.104	Project transdisciplinarity	Level of transdisciplinarity: No. of citizen/civil society organizations (e.g., NGOs) involved in the process/nature of participants	–	[#]	During stakeholder mapping and throughout project	Observation	WP2 WP9
	O.105	Systemic-climatic scenarios	Usefulness of global climate scenarios to initiate a downscaling chain to local scenarios	WP4	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP4
	O.106	Indicator application across sectors	Extent to which indicators defined in WP5 were useful in sectors beyond those predefined in the Grant Agreement	WP5	[#]	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.107	Multi-scale application	Extent to which risk assessment is capable of addressing different scales	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP5
	O.108	Scenario interdisciplinarity	No. of topics/sectors covered by climate scenarios (health, economy, environment, behaviour, etc.)	WP5	[#]	During scenario mapping and throughout project	Observation	WP5

Details Dimension	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.109	Cross-sectoral cooperation	No. of cross-sectoral working groups established in the course of the project	WP6	[#]	Once in the middle, once at the end of the project	Observation	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.110	Streamlining sectoral interaction	No. of inconsistencies (e.g., different levels of ambition; conflicts) identified and removed in interplay between sector strategies (e.g., company targets) and government strategies	–	[#]	Biannually	Observation	WP6 External stakeholders
	O.111	Climate change as cross-cutting issue	Extent to which adaptation and mitigation are also integrated into non-climate strategies	WP6	[#] of measures/strategies + Score	Biannually	Observation/Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.112	Tangible and concrete actions	Extent to which non-policy actors feel able to deduct concrete individual actions from finalized DSS	–	Score	Final year of project	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders
	O.113	Cross-sector finance	Confidence as to how well models are applicable across sectors / scales	WP7	Score / Qualitative responses	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders WP7
	O.114	Fit between input and output	Extent to which multi-scale and cross-sectoral input is mirrored by multi-scale and cross-sectoral output	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	WP8 Case studies External stakeholders

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Dimension</div>	#	Name	Description	Co-owner	Unit	Measurement interval	Method	Addressee
	O.115	Cross-scale usability	Extent to which there exist differences in the perceived usability and intuitiveness of the DSS according to different scales of case studies	–	Score	Biannually	Survey	Case studies External stakeholders

4.2 Impacts

Table 6: DISTENDER impacts and related outcomes

#	Name	Description	Outcomes linked and outcome specification
I.1	Reproduction of method for socioeconomic scenario building	Co-creation method is taken up by follower case studies to design and evaluate socioeconomic scenarios	O.1 O.3.a: Socioeconomic scenario workshops O.4 O.9 O.10
I.2	Co-creation to develop climate strategies	Co-creation is used widely to address the challenges of climate change and design solutions to them	O.1 O.4 O.8 O.9 O.45 O.66 O.117
I.3	Co-creative vulnerability assessment	Climate change impact and vulnerability assessments are sustainably improved by integrating co-creation elements	O.1 O.5 O.8 O.12 O.13 O.14
I.4	Scenario legitimization	Scenarios developed are the product of an inclusive and participatory process	O.6.a: All scenario workshops O.7 O.8 O.10 O.14 O.117
I.5	Perceived legitimacy of climate change solutions	Citizens regard climate change solutions as legitimate	O.8 O.9 O.10 O.11 O.14

			0.61
1.6	Engagement of external finance stakeholders	DISTENDER project results are acknowledged and utilized throughout financial sector	0.12 0.13 0.14 0.39 0.57 0.82
1.7	Engagement of the general public	DISTENDER stimulates engagement and participation of broader civil society	0.15 0.16 0.17 0.42 0.45 0.52 0.61 0.65
1.8	DSS as basis for lasting resilience structures	The DSS can form the foundation for potentially lasting structures on climate change resilience	0.18 0.19 0.20 0.21 0.22
1.9	Climate change networking best practice	New best practices for climate change networking are developed and shared	0.1 0.2 0.15 0.18 0.19
1.10	Climate change action structures	Fora, platforms, or roundtables for the promotion of climate change action lasting beyond project end are established	0.20 0.21 0.22
1.11	Usability of SSPs	Policymakers can utilize Socioeconomic Pathways in policy design	0.23.a: Socioeconomic scenario guidelines 0.26.a: Socioeconomic scenario integration potential 0.29

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			O.30 O.62
I.12	Usability of risk assessments	Risk assessments for the developed scenarios are suitable for informing policy design	O.23.c: Risk assessment guidelines O.24 O.26.c: Risk assessment integration potential O.30 O.33 O.66
I.13	Usability of climate scenarios	Policymakers are able to utilize climate scenarios in policy design	O.23.b: Climate scenario guidelines O.26.b: Climate scenario integration potential O.28 O.29 O.30 O.34 O.50 O.66 O.71
I.14	Aligning climate science and climate strategies	Communicative barriers between researchers and policymakers generally are identified and overcome	O.23.a+b+c O.24 O.29 O.36 O.38 O.66
I.15	Communication within large research projects	Communicative barriers between researchers and case studies are identified and overcome	O.24 O.27 O.28 O.30 O.36

I.16	Streamlining climate policymaking horizontally	Conflicts and overcomplex governance and institutional structures are streamlined (horizontally)	O.31 O.37 O.38 O.79
I.17	Streamlining climate policymaking vertically	Climate policy is streamlined across governance levels (top-to-bottom or bottom-to-top)	O.37 O.38 O.76 O.77 O.79
I.18	Transferability of results of large research projects	Follower case studies are able to transfer and implement project results	O.29 O.30 O.43 O.65 O.80 O.81
I.19	Local climate scenario development	Future climate scenario development can better integrate local factors	O.25.b: Climate scenarios O.32 O.35 O.51 O.68 O.69 O.70
I.20	Capacity of policymakers to apply cost-efficient climate scenarios	Policymakers are able to use cost-efficient (downscaled) climate scenarios or derived indicators	O.25.e: Cost-benefit analysis O.39 O.40 O.42.b: Climate scenarios O.43 O.71
I.21	Model or scenario transferability and reproducibility	Climate scenarios or models are replicable or usable beyond core case studies	O.25.b: Climate scenarios O.26 O.34 O.44

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			0.66 0.68 0.69 0.95
I.22	Climate change impact planning	Cities are better able to project climate change impacts and risks in their specific context	O.25.c: Risk assessments 0.72 0.73 0.74 0.70
I.23	Localized climate risk assessment	Adapting risk assessment methodology to better cater for local-scale requirements	O.25.c: Risk assessments 0.67 0.72 0.74 0.75
I.24	Reproducibility of strategies beyond core case studies	Strategies designed have impact beyond core case studies	O.25.d: Climate strategies O.101
I.25	New financial schemes	New and innovative financial schemes are implemented	0.45 O.82.a: Financial schemes O.100
I.26	New business models	New and innovative business models are implemented	0.45 O.82.b: Business models
I.27	DSS boosts cost-efficiency	Use of DSS results in increased cost-efficiency of climate policy	0.85 0.86 0.87 0.88 0.88 0.90
I.28	Awareness of connection between socioeconomic factors and climate change	Socioeconomic factors are better understood as drivers of vulnerability to climate change	0.45 0.46 0.48 0.49

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1.29	Conceptual clarity and innovation in climate change discourse	DISTENDER contributes to climate change discourse through conceptual innovation and increased conceptual clarity	O.45 O.46 O.47 O.49 O.52 O.53
1.30	Anchoring of climate adaptation and climate mitigation in discourse as strongly interlinked fields of action	Adaptation and mitigation are conceptually and discursively interlinked and not treated as two separate fields of action	O.53 O.54 O.55 O.56 O.60
1.31	Increased awareness of specific climate change issues	Focal and innovative DISTENDER topics gain visibility and reception throughout interested public (e.g., journalists)	O.58 O.94 O.99 O.108 O.111
1.32	Enhanced ambition for climate adaptation measures	Motivation and ambition for local-level adaptation action are boosted	O.57 O.78.a: Adaptation O.83.a: Adaptation O.84 O.89 O.93 O.58
1.33	Enhanced ambition for climate mitigation measures	Motivation and ambition for local-level mitigation action are boosted	O.57 O.58 O.78.b: Mitigation O.83.b: Mitigation O.84 O.89 O.92

I.34	Anchoring of climate adaptation and climate mitigation in policy as strongly interlinked fields of action	Adaptation and mitigation are interlinked in climate change policy and individual measures	O.59 O.96 O.98 O.99 O.94 O.100
I.35	Multi-disciplinary integration of climate action	Climate action proliferates across disciplines and sectors, leading to cross-sectoral solutions for climate change	O.64 O.104 O.105 O.108 O.109 O.111 O.113
I.36	Usability of global climate models for producing local-level scenarios	Global climate models (Earth System Models) can be utilized to develop scenarios at local scale	O.64 O.105 O.106 O.107 O.108 O.63
I.37	Sectoral mitigation innovation	Measures for climate mitigation are newly introduced in sectors	Specify the sectors O.109 O.110 O.111 O.112 O.113 O.114 O.115
I.38	Sectoral adaptation innovation	Measures for climate adaptation are newly introduced in sectors	Specify the sectors O.102 O.109 O.110 O.111 O.112 O.113

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			O.114 O.115
I.39	National/local level conflict	Additional/new inconsistencies between EU and local level due to excessive focus on local level	
I.40	Inefficient policymaking	Increase in expert input required to develop adaptation and mitigation strategies	
I.41	Neglect of other policy goals	Focus on CA/CM in combination leads to neglect of other goals (biodiversity, social impact, resource efficiency)	
I.42	Lack of context-sensitivity	Financial inputs developed for one pilot study potentially harmful in other pilot studies (e.g., because of different local regulation)	
I.43	Negative impacts on other SDGs	Extent to which WP results potentially harm other SDG areas, such as biodiversity ('do no significant harm')	
I.44	Social justice	Evaluation of who profits from the measures implemented through the project and whether climate action leads to increased social injustice and inequality	

Conclusions

To summarise, WP10 will monitor and evaluate DISTENDER's progress by means of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from an early stage of the project. The KPIs and their change in value over time will help the whole project consortium gain a clearer picture of what actions need to be taken, which aspects of the work should be prioritized and focused on, and what should be avoided. A theory of change was developed for the project to provide signpost for the development of the specific indicators. The indicators themselves provide a focus on the success of the project and efficiency of results by describing and quantifying the impact pathways. The KPIs represent a precondition for DISTENDER to achieve optimal outcomes (within the project) and impacts (outside the project). To do so, DISTENDER has identified 115 outcomes divided into ten dimensions which reflect the project objectives. These outcomes are different in their nature and different methods are employed to collect and assess them: surveys, interviews, and observations are brought together to cross-verify the quality of specific outcomes. The ten dimensions cover all the steps, procedures and elements of the project. 44 impacts are measured and calculated by interlinking them with corresponding outcomes. Their quantification is intended to support DISTENDER in achieving its goals, tracing the effectiveness of its actions and communicating them to both external and internal stakeholders.

The monitoring phase will start after the publication of the present report. In the first measurement round, baselines for most indicators will be established. The subsequent monitoring rounds will then track the change over the project duration. The framework presented in this report has purposefully been supplemented with extensive theoretical backing. This will make possible necessary adaptations and continuous reflection on the content of the precise indicators:

Monitoring itself is a process, and there are no one-fits-all approaches when it comes to monitoring and evaluating complex interventions like DISTENDER. Thus, being ready to continuously reflect on and, if needed, modify indicator sets is crucial for successful impact monitoring (cf. Himmelstein et al. 2017: 35-39). The theory of change itself should also be flexible and "midstream corrections" should be made as necessary (Roberts and Khattri 2012: 10). With regard to the KPIs measuring DISTENDER's outcomes, the list was designed as comprehensive and exhaustive as possible so as not to miss any potential outcomes of the project. This does not mean that each and every outcome must necessarily be measured as sketched in this report; reformulation or deletion of individual indicators is possible within the framework and likely. Any future changes made to the indicators presented here will be noted and argued for accordingly by the monitoring team.

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Annex I: List of EU projects consulted

Details Name	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>4I-TRACTION</u> ¹	2021-2024	Climate policy	EU governance framework; Energy policies; Climate-neutral innovation; Investment and finance	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>ARSINOE</u>	2021-2025	Smart cities Adaptation	Socio-economic impact assessment Nature resources management System innovation Vulnerability analysis	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>ARTACLIM</u>	2017-2020	Adaptation; Climate resilience	Vulnerability analysis Sensitivity analysis Nature resources management	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>CAMPAIGNERS</u>	2021-2024	Climate action Mitigation	Climate policy Technology	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>CityxChange</u>	2018-2023	Smart cities	Climate co-creation E-mobility	# Events organized # Citizen observatories established	<u>D7.3: Data Collation, Management and Analysis Methodology Framework</u>

¹ All websites linked were last accessed on 18 October 2022.

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
			Smart positive energy strategies Integrated planning and design Energy market	# Community participation # Municipal staff trained to use decision support tools # Changes in regulation # People trained # Projects implemented in follower cities	
<u>CLARITY</u>	2017-2020	Adaptation; climate scenarios and integrated assessment	Hazard assessment Urban infrastructure development Climate policy Social-innovation assessment Communication and dissemination plan	# Cities with climate change and disaster risk reduction strategies # Communication products developed % Participants who report having benefitted from an event # EU companies that participated in an event organised/supported # People trained # Events organized # Stakeholders participating in public consultations	N/A
<u>COACCH</u>	2017-2021	Climate policy; Climate action	Risks assessment of climate change Socio-economic tipping points Stakeholder involvement	# Downscaled climate assessments # Workshops # Organizations involved Survey results regarding stakeholders' needs and awareness Quality of co-design process Quality of stakeholder involvement	2811-COACCH-Co-creation-guideline-web.pdf

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
				Level of stakeholders' collaboration; Identification of key policy processes	
<u>Connecting Nature</u>	2017-2022	Adaptation Mitigation Biodiversity Cities and urban resilience	Nature-based solutions Integrated assessment Social cohesion and community creation Sustainable economic development Social enterprise Urban planning	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>CRISI-ADAPT II</u>	2019-2022	Adaptation	Climate risk assessment Climate projections Extreme hazards	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>DAREnet</u>	2017-2023	Civil protection	Flood management; Water rescue; Innovative technologies for warning system	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>ECONADAPT</u>	2013-2016	Cost-benefit analysis; Adaptation	Economics of adaptation; Policy analysis; Cost-benefit analysis	Climate model uncertainties # Stakeholders represented per focus group	Deliverable D4-3-Final approved for publishing.pdf (econadapt.eu)
<u>EU 1.5 Lifestyles</u>	2021-2025	Sustainable lifestyle	Climate policies;	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
			Socio-economic structures; Health impact assessment; Low-carbon transformative strategies; Actors' engagement		
<u>ENGAGE</u>	2020-2023	Societal resilience	Emergency management; Adaptation; Model development	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>GrowSmarter</u>	2015-2019	Smart growth	Low energy districts; Sustainable mobility; Integrated infrastructures	Evaluation of data quality	N/A
<u>IMPETUS</u>	2021-2025	Adaptation Resilience	Networking; Creation resilience knowledge boosters; Local community engagement	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>IMPRESSIONS</u>	2013-2018	Adaptation and mitigation	Community engagement; Scenario analysis; Integrated assessment; Mitigation and adaptation tipping points	No indicators developed	N/A

Details Name	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>INSPIRATION</u>	2015-2018	Resources management	Soil and land management	# Stakeholders participating in public consultations	
<u>MATCHUP</u>	2017-2022	Mitigation	Community engagement; Integrated assessment; DSS indicator framework; Energy efficiency and mobility; Societal demands	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>Life Sec Adapt</u>	2015-2018	Environmental and energy data monitoring system	Socio-economic impact assessment Communication and awareness Networking	Level of awareness on adaptation measures Increased knowledge on climate adaptation process Increase of stakeholders' participation in focal meetings Stakeholders' agreement on terminology definition Total land area affected by the project # Website visits # Email contacts addressed by newsletters # individuals reached during press conferences # Newly employed individuals Adding cost for additional staff	D1_Final_Monitoring_report.pdf (lifeseCADAPT.eu)

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>LOCOMOTION</u>	2019-2023	Sustainability transition	Development of robust methodologies and tools Improving the legitimacy and usability of project's models, methods and tools through greater transparency and user-friendliness	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>mySMARTLife</u>	2016-2022	Sustainable cities	Inclusive cities; Smart people and economy; Sustainable mobility; Building and energy efficiency; Sustainable mobility, ICT solutions; Integrated urban transformation strategy	Identification of city's challenges	N/A

<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>NAVIGATE</u>	2019-2023	Mitigation	Integrated assessment modelling; Economy and Technology; Lifestyle changes; SDGs	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>NDC ASPECTS</u>	2021-2024	Climate action	Gender responsive mitigation; Networking; Mobility; Emission-intensive industries and buildings; Agriculture, land use and forestry	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>PARIS REINFORCE</u>	2019-2022	Energy transition	Climate policy; Stakeholder inclusion framework; Climate modeling	# List of members # Workshops and meetings with technical partners Level of stakeholders' engagement Level of stakeholders' coordination Level of stakeholders' participation at meetings Risk assessment Legitimacy of models and methods	D1.1 Quality Management Plan.pdf (paris-reinforce.eu)

<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>PE4TRANS</u>	2018-2023	Sustainable mobility	Transport policies; Mobility behaviour; Engagement;	# Participants and citizens reached; # Visitor in social media # People reached through hastags # Citizen participation on online meetings # People reached by the campaign Level of stakeholders' awareness	file_1643788527.pdf (inter-regeurope.eu)
<u>POCITYF</u>	2019-2024	Smart cities	Nature-based solutions; Energy buildings and districts; Energy storage and management; E-mobility; Co-creation	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>REGILIENCE</u>	2021-2025	Climate-resilient cities	Communication; Networking; Local capacity building; Citizens' engagement; Collaboration with other projects	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>RESIN</u>	2015-2018	Climate-resilient cities and infrastructures	Development of decision support tools; Disaster risk management;	Stakeholders' engagement and co-creation Cost efficiency analysis of the project	D1-1-SOTADecisionSupport-TNO-20151130.pdf (resin-cities.eu)

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
			Adaptation; Urban planning	Level of experts' understanding and agreement Level of experts' satisfaction on developed scenarios Quality of data to predict future scenarios	
<u>SENTINEL</u>	2019-2022	Energy transition	Mitigation; Community engagement; Scenario analysis; Integrated Assessment; Economic impacts	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>SmartEnCity</u>	2016-2022	Smart cities	Policymaker engagement Citizen engagement Project reach	Level of involvement of administration in projects # Professional stakeholders involved Extent of multilevel governance % Voter participation level # citizen associations in a city Level of citizens' participation in projects # Websites and social media links # Interactive tools # Newsletters # Discussion forums	N/A

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
				# Awareness raising campaigns	
<u>SOCLIMPACT</u>	2017-2021	Decarbonization	Integrated Assessment; Downscaled scenarios; Socioeconomic assessment; Economic modeling; Adaption and mitigation	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>TransformAr</u>	2021-2025	Adaptation	Climate and social resilience; Communication; Water services;	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>Triangulum</u>	2015-2020	Climate innovation	Sustainable mobility Energy ICT Business opportunities	# Lessons shared # Citizens involved in the project # New programs developed	

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<div style="text-align: right;">Details</div> <div style="text-align: left;">Name</div>	Duration	Thematic focus of project	Focus of indicator framework	Examples of indicators used (with unit, if applicable)	Link to relevant deliverables
<u>URBAN GreenUP</u>	2017-2022	Nature-based solutions	Water management Air quality Sustainable innovation Non-technical interventions	No indicators developed	N/A
<u>VARCITIES</u>	2020-2025	Nature-based solutions	Human-centred city Green public spaces Smart and resilient cities	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A
<u>WELLBASED</u>	2021-2025	Energy transition	Socio-health assessment; Energy poverty; Digital solutions for behavioural change; Awareness	No indicators developed yet, to be followed	N/A

[Websites of all projects listed were last accessed on 25/10/2022]